

Supporting Analysis Notes for PPG001 "Minimum bias
multiplicity distribution at $\sqrt{s} = 130$ A GeV using the
PHENIX pad chambers"

November 7, 2025

Contents

1	Introduction	3
2	Disclaimer	3
3	Analysis notes	3
	AN001 – Vertex position and $dN/d\eta$ with PC1/PC3	3
	AN002 – Multiplicity distribution (Pad Chambers)	10
	AN004 – $dN_{ch}/d\eta$ via angular correlation method	20
	AN005 – TEC/PC3 matching in real data	39
	AN014 – ZDC determination of Centrality	54
	AN015 – Minimum bias triggers and vertex determination	63
	AN018 – Determining the number of participants	72
	AN019 – Multiplicity measurements (drift chamber)	91
	AN023 – Background subtraction in drift chamber	111
	AN032 – Final Analysis Note	121

1 Introduction

This is a compilation of internal analysis notes for Phys.Rev.Lett.87(2001)112303 (Paper Preparation Group 001) by the PHENIX collaboration. This consists of several analysis notes referred to by their internal identifier. For example, analysis note 1 is referred to as AN001. All internal analysis notes submitted in support of this paper are included. This may mean that some information is duplicated elsewhere. Analysis notes may include author lists; these author lists are superseded by the published paper's author lists.

2 Disclaimer

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3 Analysis notes

Analysis Note 001 - July 19, 2000

WIS group for PHENIX collaboration

**Determination of the event vertex position
and measurement of dN/dEta using information
from PC1 and PC3 with B=0.**

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Created: May,1,2000

Updated: May,11,2000

The transparencies of the WIS group presentation at the May core meeting can be seen here: ([ps-file](#)).

This is a short summary of work done recently at the WIS on our local PC farm. We present preliminary results on vertex determination and measurement of dn/dEta using ONLY the information provided by PC1 and PC3 in the East arm.

We have generated 100 GeV/nucleon Au-Au HIJING events at various impact parameters and passed them through PISA using day one configuration of the East Arm and without magnetic field.

The analysis is based on the pisaRootRead output and does NOT include the detector response chain. However, assuming that the efficiency of PC1 and PC3 is known and close to 100% and that the resolution is not much different from what is calculated in [Analytic calculation of the PHENIX pad chamber performance](#) or as provided by simulation, the results should not be affected in any significant way. The multiple scattering is by far the dominant factor in the game.

Number of hits

The number of hits per central collision (impact parameter $b=0-2\text{fm}$) in PC1 and PC3 (based on the statistics of 500 events) are summarized in this table.

	PC1	PC3	PC1 only	PC3 only	PC1&PC3
Total	189	202	66	77	124
primaries	94	73	23	2.3	71
decays	45	86	15	55	31
background	50	42	28	20	45

We distinguish three categories of hits:

- primaries: a primary particle produced at the collision vertex and hitting the detector.
- decays: a particle produced in the decay in flight of a particle (mostly primaries), before hitting the detector.
- background: all other particles hitting the detector.

Vertex finding

Algorithm: Every hit in PC3 is combined to every hit in PC1 within an appropriate window. The resulting lines are projected onto the $X=0$ plane. The geometry of PC1 and PC3 and the projection plane can be seen in Figure 1.

Note that the projection plane is inclined by 11.25deg with respect to the real PHENIX $X=0$ plane due to the inclination of the East arm.

The distribution of all these projections along the Z axis for one single event is shown in Figure 2. The vertex position is easily and clearly determined by the peak position.

Note: this picture was updated from the [original](#) one.

So far, for central collisions we have achieved a vertex resolution of RMS~2mm when the vertex is in the range +/-40cm. We are currently working on refining the algorithm. The vertex resolution in Z is shown in Figure 3.

The algorithm works equally well for the Y coordinate.

dN/dEta calculation

Once the vertex is known, we combine again all hits in PC3 to all hits in PC1 in a more restricted window and we plot the radius of all projections from the vertex point. The resulting R distribution for at total of 550 central events is shown Figure 4.

The figure shows also the three categories of tracks contributing to the total distribution:

Primaries (red): these are tracks made out of primary hits which are affected only by multiple scattering.

Decays (blue): tracks where at least one hit is due to a decay product of a primary particle decaying in-flight. The main component is " $\pi \rightarrow \mu + \nu$ ".

Background (black): tracks originating from background particles. Their yield increases linearly with "R".

The number of background tracks can be determined with high accuracy by using a mixed event technique or by replacing the hits in the top 4 PC1 with the hits in the bottom 4 PC1 and vice versa.

Subtracting the number of background tracks from the total number of tracks gives the measured number of charged particles related to the collision. The latter is compared below to the corresponding HIJING information.

measured: Number of reconstructed charged tracks within a radius of 20cm around the vertex.
(The splitting of this number between primary tracks and tracks from decay products is also indicated).
Hijing: total number of charged particles emitted within the fiducial acceptance of the east arm.

All numbers are given per event and are based on 500 events with $b=0-2\text{fm}$ and 200 events with $b=2-8\text{fm}$.

	Measured	Primary	Decay	Hijing
0-2fm	97.3	68.3	29.0	111
2-8fm	56.2	38.8	17.4	66

The measured track multiplicity has to be corrected for:

-the finite PC3 efficiency of 93% due to dead areas.

-decays occurring outside the 20cm radius. This is a very small correction and up to now we have neglected it.

With the PC3 efficiency correction the number of measured tracks relative to the number of charged particles from HIJING becomes:

$$\text{for } b=0-2\text{fm: } \frac{97.3}{0.93 * 111} = 94\%$$

$$\text{for } b=2-8\text{fm: } \frac{56.2}{0.93 * 66} = 92\%$$

CONCLUSION: The number of charged tracks measured by PC1 and PC3, after background subtraction, is very close (larger than 90%) to the number of charged particles emitted within the fiducial acceptance of one central arm.

We have started to generate 70GeV data. With the nominal arm configuration the numbers remain very similar. As soon as the retracted configuration of PHENIX is incorporated into PISA we can provide updated results.

Analysis Note 002 - July 19, 2000

Multiplicity Distribution using the PHENIX Pad Chambers.

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July 18, 2000

This note describes the analysis procedure used to determine the multiplicity distribution of charged particles in one PHENIX central arm using the information from the Pad Chambers PC1 and PC3 with $B=0$, and it presents the raw and corrected multiplicity distribution dN/dN_{ch} as a function of N_{ch} in $|\eta| < 0.5$.

The method follows closely the Monte Carlo study presented last May [1] but with major improvements, however, this time using minimum bias events of Au-Au collisions at 130 GeV per nucleon. The results presented below are based on a total of 7206 events for which we reconstructed the collision vertex within $z = \pm 40$ cm.

1. The collision vertex is determined in an event-by-event basis, using exactly the same algorithm as in [1], i.e. combining all hits in PC3 with all hits in PC1. See [1] for details. An example of vertex finding can be seen in Fig.1 below.

Fig.1 Example of vertex reconstruction.

2. Once the vertex is known, we combine again all hits in PC3 to all hits in PC1, the PC1-3 tracks are projected to the plane $X=0$ and we plot the distance R of the intersection point to the vertex point (see the geometrical sketch in Fig.2 below).

Fig.2 Sketch of the geometry.

The resulting R distribution for all tracks found in the above sample is shown in Fig.3 below by the red curve.

Fig.3 Number of tracks vs R of the cut.

The figure also shows the two components of tracks contributing to the total distribution:

- the background contribution (in blue) determined by using a mixed event technique, namely by exchanging each sector in PC1 with its neighbour. The background yield obviously increases quadratically with R (resulting in a linear dependence in the R distribution in Fig. 3).
- the real tracks contribution (in green) which is readily obtained by subtracting the background from the total ($N_{\text{tot}} = N_{\text{real}} + N_{\text{bg}}$). One observes a sharp peak at small R - these are tracks from primary hits originating at the vertex - and a long tail due to decay products of a primary particle decaying in flight (see [1]).

In practice, the track counting is performed for all tracks up to a given R_{cut} value. The fraction of counted real tracks as a function of R_{cut} can be easily obtained by integrating the green curve and is shown in Fig.4. In the present analysis the value was set to $R_{\text{cut}} = 15$ cm, i.e.the fraction of accepted tracks is 78%.

Fig.4 Fraction of the accepted tracks as a function of R_{cut} .

3. The raw multiplicity distributions of N_{tot} and N_{bg} are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Raw multiplicity distribution of the total number of tracks (N_{tot} in red)
Raw multiplicity distribution of the background tracks (N_{bg} in blue)

4. The background subtraction is a critical step. It can of course be done event-by-event. However, this would introduce an unnecessary broadening of the real multiplicity distribution. In order to avoid that, we perform an average background subtraction, exploiting the clear correlation which exists between N_{bg} and N_{tot} . Fig. 6 shows a two dimensional plot of N_{bg} (calculated event-by-event by the mixing procedure) vs. N_{tot} per event. The small horizontal bars represent the arithmetic average of N_{bg} for a given bin of N_{tot} and the vertical bar is its rms divided by \sqrt{N} where N is the number of entries in that particular bin.

Fig. 6 Scatterplot of the N_{bg} vs N_{tot} .

It can be shown (we shall do it in another occasion) from first principles and with very solid approximations, that the dependence of the average N_{bg} vs. N_{tot} can be described by the expression:

$$N_{bg} = N_{tot} - 2K(\sqrt{N_{tot}/K+1})-1$$

where K is an R dependent parameter. The solid line in Fig. 6 shows the result of fitting the above expression to the N_{bg} vs N_{tot} dependence. From the above expression, one easily sees that:

$$N_{real} = 2K(\sqrt{N_{tot}/K+1})-1$$

This expression actually performs an average background subtraction and allows to obtain the multiplicity distribution of real tracks shown in Fig.7

Fig.7 Multiplicity Distribution of real tracks within a radius $R_{\text{cut}}=15\text{cm}$.

5. In order to obtain dN/dN_{ch} vs N_{ch} in one unit of rapidity the distribution has to be corrected for a series of factors:

- acceptance factor f_a :

In the retracted PHENIX geometry the single arm acceptance is:

$$|\eta| < 0.30 \quad \phi = 78\text{deg.}$$

$$f_a = 7.69$$

Fraction of counted tracks:

for R_{cut} value of 15cm

$$f_t = 0.78$$

Dead areas:

by construction in PC1	1.0%
by construction in PC3 theta	4.0%
by construction in PC3 phi	4.5%
due to inactive channels in PC1	1.3%
due to inactive channels in PC3	3.5%
Dead area correction factor	

$$f_d = .86$$

Total factor:

$$f = 11.4$$

In addition, we still have to apply the following corrections:

- single hit efficiency in the pad chambers (estimated to be better than 99% from the detector response compared to Monte Carlo);
- track pile-up (estimated to be negligibly small);
- correction for the spread of the vertex along the Z axis. (estimated to be small).

- The amount of decay particles depend on the momentum distribution of the primaries. Not having any knowledge about it, we cannot estimate the amount of decays which escape detection. If we assume that the momentum distribution as given by HIJING is correct, then there is an additional increase of app. 5%

The distribution shown in Fig.8 is obtained by applying the known correction factor of 11.4 only.

Fig.8 Multiplicity distribution measured in one PHENIX arm. See text for details.

6. Preliminary Error analysis.

- Two main factors affect the shape of the raw multiplicity distribution at the highest multiplicities:

- a) The limited acceptance of one single arm equal to 13% (1/7.69). This results in a broadening of the distribution given by the sigma of the binomial distribution with mean $N \sim 600$ and probability $f = 0.13$, i.e. variance = $600 \times 0.13 \times 0.87$ and sigma = 8 charged particles out of a measured value of app.55. See Fig.7.

b) the effect of the R_{cut} value of 15 cm. As shown above, with this value we count 78% of all real tracks. This results also in a binomial distribution broadening which at the highest value of N_{real} gives a variance = $Nf(1-f) = 55 \times .78$ or $\sigma = 3.5$ particles.

- The main factors affecting the absolute scale of the multiplicity distribution are:

- * the background subtraction i.e. the error in K (not yet calculated but estimated to be better than 5%).
- * the error in the other correction factors listed in 5 are all relatively negligible.
- * the error in the (not yet applied) correction due to decays which escape detection.

Weizmann group

Analysis Note 004 - August 15, 2000

The Determination of $\frac{dN_{ch}}{d\eta}$ for Minimum Bias Au+Au Data at $\sqrt{s} = 130$ GeV Using the Angular Correlation Method for Associating PC1 and PC3

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August 10, 2000

Contents

- [Contents](#)
- [List of Figures](#)
- [Introduction](#)
- [Analysis Method](#)
- [Simulation Results for Central Collisions](#)
- [Minimum Bias Results Using Real Data](#)
 - [Angular Correlation Results for Real Data](#)
 - [Angular Correlation Results for Intra-Event Mixed Data](#)
 - [Extracted Track Multiplicity Spectra](#)
 - [Angular Correlation Results for Intra-Event Mixed Data](#)
- [Simulation Analysis of Real Minimum Bias Results](#)
- [Summary and Future Work](#)
- [Prior PHENIX communications about measuring \$\frac{dN_{ch}}{d\eta}\$ with PC1/PC3](#)
- [CAMERA Macro Modifications for This Analysis](#)

List of Figures

- [Initial simulation of the PC1/PC3 angular correlation for central collision HIJING events conducted at a fixed \$Z_0 = 0\$ vertex with retracted arms and at \$\sqrt{s} = 140\$ GeV.](#)
- [Deconvolution and efficiencies for PC1/PC3 correlation after a 1.0 degree angle cut of HIJING central collision events simulated in the previous figure.](#)
- [Deconvolution and efficiencies for PC1/PC3 correlation after a 0.7 degree angle cut of HIJING central collision events simulated in the previous figure.](#)
- [The correlation angle projections for PC1/PC3 associated clusters as found by the minimum angle sum algorithm for a set of ten \$\sqrt{s} = 130\$ GeV PRDFs.](#)

- [The correlation angle projections for PC1/PC3 associated clusters as found by the minimum angle sum algorithm for a set of ten \$\sqrt{s} = 130\$ GeV PRDFs, without using BBC Z0 shift.](#)
- [The correlation angle projections for West Arm PC1 and East Arm PC3 accidentally associated clusters as found with the same algorithm.](#)
- [The track multiplicity spectra based on a 1 degree correlation angle cut.](#)
- [The track multiplicity spectra based on a 1 degree correlation angle cut using MIXED events.](#)
- [The simulation prediction for HIJING track multiplicities seen by PC1/PC3 in retracted arms geometry, and including noise contributions](#)
- [Comparison of measured track multiplicity spectrum with predicted multiplicity spectrum from HIJING 1.35 as processed with the same angular correlation cuts.](#)
- [Comparison of measured track multiplicity spectrum with predicted multiplicity spectrum from HIJING 1.35 as processed with a smaller 0.85 degree angular correlation cut.](#)
- [Primary particle multiplicity in PC1 along the Z axis \(lab frame\) for 2000 minimum bias HIJING 1.35 events from Z0 = 0 cm \(top\) and Z0 = 40 cm \(bottom\).](#)
- [Deconvolution and efficiencies for PC1/PC3 correlation after a 1.0 degree angle cut of HIJING minimum bias collision events simulated in Fig. 8.](#)

Introduction

This analysis note describes a measurement of the $\frac{dN_{ch}}{d\eta}$ for the initial set of Au+Au $\sqrt{s} = 130$ GeV minimum bias data

taken by the PHENIX detector. These data were taken in late June and early July 2000. The measurement uses the PC1/PC3 angular correlation method, which our group has been studying in simulation since late April. We have included a careful study of some of the systematic errors which is of particular importance considering that the PC1/PC3 geometry is non-optimal for this measurement.

This Analysis Note begins with a description of the angular correlation method for associating clusters in PC1 and PC3 at zero magnetic field. That section is followed by a review of our initial central collision simulations which established the feasibility of doing such a track multiplicity measurement with PC1/PC3. The next section presents the analysis of a set of real data at $\sqrt{s} = 130$ GeV using the angular correlation method for PC1/PC3 association. Track multiplicity spectra are

presented. The fifth section gives the simulation analysis of these results using HIJING1.35 events, including systematic error analysis. The last section concludes with a set of action items needed for future analysis work.

Analysis Method

Figure 1: Initial simulation of the PC1/PC3 angular correlation for central collision HIJING events conducted at a fixed $Z_0 = 0$ vertex with retracted arms and at $\sqrt{s} = 140$ GeV.

The analysis method uses the angular correlation in polar angle ($\equiv \theta$) and azimuthal angle ($\equiv \phi$) between PC1 and PC3 in order to establish particle tracks that point back to the collision vertex. Given a zero magnetic field working in a collision frame whose origin is at the Z_0 of the collision, primary charged particles will travel along trajectories of constant θ and

constant ϕ , if multiple scattering and in-flight decays are ignored.

We used the Z_0 value from the BBC subsystem in order to determine the θ values at PC1 and PC3. This allows for the determination of $\frac{dN_{ch}}{d\eta}$ at the lowest multiplicities accessible by the BBC trigger. By contrast, the WIS group initially employed a method that determined Z_0 by the PC1 and PC3. This method works well but is limited to events with approximately ten or more tracks in the East Arm. Above that limit, the WIS group has found that they obtain the same results using the Z_0 determined from the BBC and from PC1 and PC3.

In the angular correlation method the difference angles $\Delta\theta_{13}$ and $\Delta\phi_{13}$ are computed for all possible PC1-PC3 associations. The PC3 cluster selected for a candidate primary particle track is the one for which the sum $|\Delta\theta_{13}| + |\Delta\phi_{13}|$ is a minimum.

In Fig. 1 we show the results of a simulation study using central collision HIJING events all at $Z_0 = 0$. In this example, the GEANT simulation included all physics reactions such as in-flight decay, reactions, and multiple scattering. One thing which is not included so far in simulations is the Pad Chamber detector response software. Also not included is the actual cluster finder software used in the real event reconstruction. Instead, both the WIS and the VU groups have used the *pisaRootRead* utility function to process the simulated PC hits from PISA. This is a known deficiency in the simulation analysis which needs to be overcome.

The two plots at the top show the θ and ϕ angular correlation between PC1 and PC3 for hits caused by primary particles in PC1. The hits are correlated using the PC1-PC3 angular correlation method described above. One can see that the association algorithm has been largely successful, and that there is a very tight correlation for these primary particles.

The bottom two plots show correlations for particles at PC1 and PC3 that are the result of decays. These plots include decays of neutral as well as charged primaries. As expected, the angular correlation becomes broader when decays are allowed. Finally, one can see the mechanical gaps in the PC3 construction. The gap at $Z=0$ corresponds to $\theta = 90^\circ$ with this $Z_0 = 0$ collision vertex value. There are also three gaps in the PC3 acceptance in ϕ between sectors that are clearly visible. These gaps contribute to the loss in signal efficiency.

Figure 2: Deconvolution and efficiencies for PC1/PC3 correlation after a 1.0 degree angle cut of HIJING central collision events simulated in the previous figure.

Simulation Results for Central Collisions

The initial quantitative results of the PC1-PC3 angular correlation algorithm are shown in Fig. 2. These studies are for central

collisions and we will show the results to be somewhat different for minimum bias collisions. The PC1-PC3 associated hits are required to have $\Delta\theta_{13}$ and $\Delta\phi_{13}$ each less than 1 degree. For pedagogical reasons, the results of this cut are shown as a momentum spectrum. First, in the upper right plot the results are shown for the PC1-PC3 correlation where both hits are caused by the same primary particle. The efficiency of this cut is 94% relative to the number of primaries in PC1 that are correctly associated in PC3 when the angle cut is wide open.

The middle two plots show the results for decay of pions and kaons into muons. In the left of these plots the decay occurs between PC1 and PC3. In the right middle plot, the decay occurs before PC1 and the daughter muon was correctly associated in both PC1 and PC3. Unsurprisingly, the efficiency for correctly associating the in-flight decays is substantially smaller than for the primaries. Note also the differences in the mean momenta of these three panels, an effect of the momentum-dependent decay probabilities as seen in the lab frame.

The lower left plot shows the accidental correlations of primaries in PC1. The lower right plot shows the contribution of decays of neutral primaries. This latter plot represents background to the measurement of the primary charged particle distribution.

The sum of entries in the second through the fifth plots constitutes the primary charged particle signal. The top left plot shows signal plus noise. For a 1 degree correlation cut the signal is 82% of the total, while the noise contribution consists of the 12% from neutral particle descendant contributions and 6% coming from descendants of primary charged particles which give accidental associations between PC1 and PC3. (This latter contribution is not plotted separately.)

An important systematic check is to vary the cut angle. Fig. 3 shows a similar set of plots as in Fig. 2, using the same set of simulated central collision events, but with a smaller, 0.7 degree angular correlation cut. One sees that while the signal yield decreases by 8%, the noise yield drops by a greater fraction, resulting in a signal-to-noise increase from 82% to 86%.

Figure 3: Deconvolution and efficiencies for PC1/PC3 correlation after a 0.7 degree angle cut of HIJING central collision events simulated in the previous figure.

Minimum Bias Results Using Real Data

Angular Correlation Results for Real Data

The angular correlation results using real data taken with the arms retracted and zero field are shown in Fig. 4. The data in this figure were processed from the set of ten runs numbered 5935 to 6034. These PRDF files are dated July 4-5 in the /phenix/data06/evt_data public area. The PRDFs were processed using a slightly modified version of the camDataRun.C, camDataIni.C, and camDataPar.C macro file. Details of these modifications are given in Appendix B. As of August 8, new data files with zero field have been taken with the non-retracted geometry. We expect that these data will be processed soon after the completion of this Analysis Note.

Figure 4: The correlation angle projections for PC1/PC3 associated clusters as found by the minimum angle sum algorithm for a set of ten $\sqrt{s} = 130$ GeV PRDFs.

In Fig. 4, one can see that the azimuthal correlation is fairly sharp, but the polar angle correlation is broader. Analysis done in early July (before July 19) showed that the polar angle correlation was sharper then. We believe that a problem with the BBC calibration for these runs may be causing extra broadening in the polar angle correlation. A more serious problem is shown in Fig. 5. The polar correlation peak is displaced significantly away from 0 degrees if one uses the Z vertex value actually returned by the BBC software. This problem has been corrected in Fig. 4 by artificially shifting the BBC Z vertex by 6.0 cm.

The observed shift indicates some longitudinal misalignment in either PC1, PC3, the BBC, or some combination of the three. Other work has shown that the PC3 longitudinal alignment is close to that of the TOF and that the PC1 is aligned with the DC. Furthermore, there is a sizeable (≈ 5 cm) systematic difference in comparing the BBC and ZDC Z vertex measurements¹. Thus the greatest suspicion is directed at the BBC, a detail which must be reconciled in future studies².

Figure 5: The correlation angle projections for PC1/PC3 associated clusters as found by the minimum angle sum algorithm for a set of ten PRDFs, without using BBC Z0 shift.

Angular Correlation Results for Intra-Event Mixed Data

Figure 6: The correlation angle projections for West Arm PC1 and East Arm PC3 accidentally associated clusters as found with the same algorithm.

Since the PHENIX Central Arm detectors have a North-South symmetry, and sometimes an East-West symmetry, an obvious experimental check on accidental associations in tracking results is to do a geography swap. In this case we have chosen to do an East-West swap of PC1. The West Arm PC1 clusters are attempted to be matched with the East Arm PC3 clusters. Naturally, all the association results must be accidental backgrounds. The shape of this accidental association can be used to estimate the background contribution to the real East PC1 and East PC3 cluster associations.

Extracted Track Multiplicity Spectra

A minimum bias event sample track multiplicity spectrum was extracted from this real data sample using a 1.0 degree angular correlation cut. These results are shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: The track multiplicity spectra based on a 1 degree correlation angle cut.

The sample is limited to those events having a vertex from -18 to $+18$ cm, with the original data sample having 23,981 events. A comparison with the plot shows that the ± 18 cm cut discards 90% of the original data in the PRDFs. A justification for this stringent cut will be given below.

Fig. 6 shows that the mean number of tracks is 21.5, with an RMS of 22. There are two caveats to the above plot. First, the plot includes background to combinatorics as well as the physics processes discussed above.

The second caveat is that the mean number of tracks as compared to an event generator prediction could be sensitive to the BBC trigger efficiency. If the BBC trigger is missing very peripheral events, which would produce few or no tracks in the Pad Chambers, then the observed mean track value would tend to be too high.

Angular Correlation Results for Intra-Event Mixed Data

A necessary cross check for our result is to generate the intra-event mixing spectrum. As before, we correlate hits in PC1 West with hits in PC3 East for our event sample, and apply the same ± 18 cm vertex cut. The results of this intra-event mixing are shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: The track multiplicity spectra based on a 1 degree correlation angle cut using MIXED events.

This spectrum does not directly represent the background in Fig. 6. For example, if one assumed that all the clusters in PC1 West were primaries, then the above spectrum is telling us something about the probability that these primaries would be associated falsely associated in PC3 if the primary particle was not in PC3. The intra-event mixed spectrum is an overestimate of the background in the non-mixed spectrum.

Simulation Analysis of Real Minimum Bias Results

Figure 9: The simulation prediction for HIJING track multiplicities seen by PC1/PC3 in retracted arms geometry, and including noise contributions

Before the real data PRDFs were processed, we conducted the equivalent analysis on a set of 2000 minimum bias HIJING 1.35 events, tracked through PISA2000 in retracted geometry with zero magnetic field. The same angular correlation algorithm was used on this simulated data, albeit in the *pisaRootRead* utility, as was done with the PC cluster outputs from the event reconstruction software. These HIJING events were all at a fixed $Z_0 = 0$ cm vertex. The result of this simulation exercise is shown in Fig. 9.

Initially, there appears to be a fair agreement between the HIJING predicted results and the real data results. Note that the HIJING predicted results, in this method, also include the "noise" component as previously defined in Section 2. To the extent that the analysis of the simulated data is an accurate representation of the real data processing, Fig. 9 shows the HIJING prediction corrected for the acceptance of the PC1/PC3 geometry, as well as the "noise" performance of the correlation algorithm.

Figure 10: Comparison of measured track multiplicity spectrum with predicted multiplicity spectrum from HIJING 1.35 as processed with the same angular correlation cuts.

In Fig. 10 we plot the experimentally measured track multiplicity and the simulated track multiplicity spectrum together to show better the quality of the agreement³.

The Fig. 10 comparison is done with a correlation angular cut of 1 degree in both θ and ϕ . In principle, the comparison between the measured spectrum and the simulated spectrum should not depend upon the value of the angle cut, provided that the simulation accurately includes all the signal and noise sources. So as a further check, we have reduced the angular cut from 1.0 to 0.85 degrees. Fig. 11 shows the theory-to-experiment comparison for the 0.85 degree correlation angle cut.

Figure 11: Comparison of measured track multiplicity spectrum with predicted multiplicity spectrum from HIJING 1.35 as processed with a smaller 0.85 degree angular correlation cut.

Both the experimental spectrum and the predicted spectrum shift towards lower multiplicities with the smaller angle cut. One can still say that there is fair agreement between the prediction and the measurement. However, the mean track multiplicity value for the experimental spectrum has decreased by 9% while the mean track multiplicity value for the HIJING spectrum has decreased by 5%. One cannot say what is the source of this discrepancy since both the simulation and HIJING are not expected to be perfect representations of the data. Nonetheless, one can say that there is not a dramatic change in the quality of the agreement given a substantial change in the cut parameter of the analysis.

At present, we know that there is a problem of the BBC Z vertex having to be shifted 6 cm, and the θ correlation peak is wider in this analysis than we found in early July. So we know that there are at least those curable defects in the current data⁴.

The accuracy of the simulation prediction can be tested by other independent means. For example, one would want to look at the comparison between simulated and real data with the new unretracted geometry. One would also want to look at the purported East Arm PC1/PC3 tracks to see how many of these can be confirmed by association with the Drift Chamber, the TEC, the TOF, and the PbGl (sector 1 only). These cross checks would provide an independent handle on the "noise" component of the experimental multiplicity spectrum.

Figure 12: Primary particle multiplicity in PC1 along the Z axis (lab frame) for 2000 minimum bias HIJING 1.35 events from $Z_0 = 0$ cm (top) and $Z_0 = 40$ cm (bottom).

There is one obvious disconnect between the simulation prediction and analysis of the real data. The real data analysis used a continuous distribution of events from -18 to $+18$ cm, whereas the simulation used only fixed $Z_0 = 0$ HIJING events. There are two natural roads to take: 1) repeat the real data analysis with more events and subdivide the results according to the nominal BBC Z vertex value; 2) do the HIJING simulation with a continuous distribution of events. Both of these roads will be pursued in the near future.

Another systematic check which one can do is to look at a HIJING simulation with a fixed Z_0 far removed from the $Z_0 = 0$ value. We have already done this simulation systematic check, with the results shown in Fig. 12. Here we compare the primary particle multiplicities in PC1 along the Z axis for HIJING events launched at $Z=0.0$ cm and at $Z_0=40$ cm, which is just at the boundary of the nosecones. It is obvious that the nosecones induce a sharp cut off for the PC1 multiplicity. The reason for this effect is clear. The single purpose of the nosecones is to induce the primary pions and kaons to react hadronically such that their in-flight decay to muons will be a lessened background into the muon arms. The nosecones will have that same effect on primary pions and kaons which otherwise were headed to PC1 from a $Z_0=40$ cm vertex.

From the above discussion one can conclude that it is best to apply a vertex cut to select events which originate sufficiently far away from the nosecones in order to avoid artificially small track multiplicities in the event sample. How far away is sufficient remains to be determined from more systematic study. In our case we have chosen the ± 18 cm range because this range gives us 2000 events to study, which matches what we had previously used in the simulation exercise.

For our final systematic study of this Analysis Note, we present the deconvolution of the simulated minimum track multiplicity spectrum into primary and decay-in-flight components, just as we have shown earlier from the studies in May for the central collision HIJING events.

Figure 13: Deconvolution and efficiencies for PC1/PC3 correlation after a 1.0 degree angle cut of HIJING minimum bias collision events simulated in Fig. 8.

In Fig. 13 one can see that the signal-to-noise ratio for this minimum bias (HIJING 1.35) event simulation is close to the central collision (HIJING1.33) event simulation which we did in May. Also, the primary particle cut efficiency is the same 94% seen in the previous study. On the other hand, the cut efficiency for detecting the primary particles which decay, either before or after PC1, has dropped from 64% to 54% reflecting the lower average momentum of these particles. The accidentals contribution has dropped from 4.2% to 2.4%. Such a drop is understandable on the basis of a lower average multiplicity in minimum bias events giving a lower probability for a random PC3 association with a PC1 hit. The neutral particle descendants contribution to the noise has also dropped somewhat from 12% to 11% in going from central collisions to minimum bias collisions. Whether this drop has physical significance or not, it is small enough that we do not have to worry about a large change in the neutral primary induced contribution to the track multiplicities.

Summary and Future Work

A set of minimum bias PRDFs were analyzed to determine the primary charged particle multiplicity via the PC1/PC3 angular

correlation method. This method yielded an average track multiplicity of 21.5 compared to the predicted value of 18.4 from a HIJING 1.35 simulation. At this point we would not claim that this difference is significant since the mean track multiplicity comparison depends upon the experimental trigger efficiencies for the the most peripheral events. For that matter, there has been recent discussion about how to best run the HIJING event generator for minimum bias events.

Apart from the mean value, the overall shape of the experimentally determined track multiplicity spectrum was in reasonable agreement with the simulated prediction from HIJING.

There are still several important tasks to do before a physics publication can be completed. Here we list some of those tasks:

- 1 The zero field data with unretracted arms must be analyzed. This would provide two new, closer planes of tracking information and give us another handle on our systematics for in-flight decays. The geometric acceptances are also intrinsically higher for the unretracted, designed geometry.
- 2 Both the unretracted data and the retracted data must be simulated through the event reconstruction chain instead of the idealized *pisaRootRead* utility function. There have been recent technical problems with the Pad Chamber detector response software in PHOOL which have prevented this more realistic simulation from being done.
- 3 The actual Pad Chamber efficiencies should be determined, ideally using external gating detectors. Since the Pad Chambers are in principle highly efficient it is not particularly easy to determine precisely the expected small inefficiencies. However, an attempt should be made to see that nothing unforeseen is transpiring with the Pad Chamber efficiencies.
- 4 More systematic studies need to be done of the dependence of the multiplicity spectrum on the cutoff due to the nosecones. In addition, we should study the effect of changing the particle momentum, say $\pm 20\%$, and the effect of changing the particle composition. These effects are not expected to be show-stoppers, but need to be included in a publication to forestall questions from the readers.

In conclusion, we have extracted a charged particle multiplicity spectrum for Au + Au at $\sqrt{s} = 130$ GeV. This spectrum appears to be in reasonable agreement with a simulation of HIJING into the PC1/PC3 retracted arms acceptance.

Prior PHENIX communications about measuring $\frac{dN_{ch}}{d\eta}$ with PC1/PC3

In this appendix we summarize the recent history of internal PHENIX communications on this topic to set the context and to give credit to everyone involved so far. The idea of determining $\frac{dN_{ch}}{d\eta}$ by using the PC1+PC3 in zero field was first

publicized by Dave Morrison on April 21⁵. This was followed up by a reply on April 29 from one of us (C.F.M.)⁶ proposing to use the *pisaRootRead* software to do a feasibility study of Dave's proposal. This reply was expanded upon two days afterwards⁷ with some first encouraging numerical results. Moreover, that communication pointed out the eventual need to do significant corrections for in-flight decay of the primary charged pions and kaons. In turn this May 1 note was followed one hour later⁸ by a communication from the WIS group announcing the first WWW site^{9 10} describing their simulations for the determination of $\frac{dN_{ch}}{d\eta}$ in collisions of Au+Au at $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV using the Day 1 retracted arms geometry. The WIS

numerical results were based in part on the use of the *pisaRootRead* utility. In the following week there was another communication from the Vanderbilt group announcing a second WWW site¹¹ which showed simulation study of the PC1/PC3 angular correlation method for determining the primary particle $\frac{dN_{ch}}{d\eta}$ in central collisions. The VU study also used also the

Day 1 retracted geometry but at $\sqrt{s} = 140$ GeV collisions.

Both of these initial simulation studies reached a conclusion that a determination of the primary charged particle $\frac{dN_{ch}}{d\eta}$ would be possible for the real PHENIX data acquired at zero magnetic field. This consensus was confirmed with other members of the global PWG participating in a core week meeting at BNL on July 13. That PWG meeting was followed on July 18 by the submission from the WIS group of the two Analysis Notes [12](#) [13](#) in PHENIX applying their zero field algorithm and analysis to the first PHENIX data at $\sqrt{s} = 130$ GeV taken in late June and early July.

CAMERA Macro Modifications for This Analysis

The PRDFs were processed through a slightly modified version of the *camDataRun.C*, *camDataIni.C*, and *camDataPar.C* macro file. The modifications were

- 1 The calling argument list was expanded to allow for switches which would turn off non-needed subsystems in the interests of speed and making the chain less crash-prone.
- 2 Based on earlier results which showed "ghost clusters", the cluster splitting option was disabled.
- 3 A simple PC1-PC3 association macro *pc1pc3Corr.C* in the chain to establish the minimum sum angle condition and to write out a multi-parameter (57), portable ROOT NTUPLE¹⁴ for DST-like analysis.

About this document ...

The Determination of $\frac{dN_{ch}}{d\eta}$ for Minimum Bias

Au+Au Data at $\sqrt{s} = 130$ GeV Using the

Angular Correlation Method for Associating PC1 and PC3

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2000-09-25

Analysis Note 005 - August 16, 2000

TEC/PC3 Matching in Real Data

TEC group for the PHENIX collaboration.

Created on August 11, 2000 by [Sasha Lebedev](#)

Introduction

We present here the results on matching Tec tracks with Pc3 clusters for the data taken this summer (particular run numbers used in this analysis are noted below).

We used offline software and CAMERA macros as of July 19. To do Tec/Pc3 matching, for each Tec track we looped over all Pc3 clusters, and found the closest one. If it was within 3 sigmas of Tec/Pc3 space resolution (see below) we considered Tec track and Pc3 cluster as matched.

Only East Arm Data were used and matching was done separately for north and south sides to reduce accidental matching.

Event displays

On the following two plots small red dots are **Tec hits**, black lines are reconstructed **Tec tracks**, and **PC3 clusters** are shown by blue circles.

The plots were made for event # 36 of run 4443.

Space resolution

The following plots were made for all 284 events in run # 4443. Only south side of sectors 1 and 2 was used.

Survey geometry was used for both Tec and Pad chambers.

The first plot shows distance between Pc3 clusters and Tec tracks projected to Pc3 (black histogram). Red and blue histograms show background, calculated by **flipping Pc3 Z coordinate** or **flipping Pc3 Y coordinate**.

The space resolution is about 7mm as can be seen from the following plot.

Next plot shows the same picture, but **Geant geometry with arms retracted by 44cm** was used for **Tec**. Space resolution is the same within statistical errors, but there is 4mm shift.

Matching efficiency

Tec track was considered matched with Pc3 cluster, if there was a Pc3 cluster within 21mm (3 sigmas) of the track. Closest distance between a line (Tec track) and a point (Pc3 cluster) was used in this analysis.

Tec/Pc3 matching efficiency (averaged over all Tec multiplicities) is shown as a function of number of Tec hits associated with Tec track. By increasing this cut it is possible to reject "ghost" tracks in Tec. As can be seen from the plot, matching efficiency increases with increased cut on number of hits, due to rejection of "ghost" tracks. Maximum average (over all multiplicities) matching efficiency is 75%.

The plot was made for all events in run # 4443. As will be shown below, there is multiplicity dependence of matching efficiency (probably due to larger number of ghost tracks in Tec in high multiplicity events).

Matching efficiency is somewhat decreased due to the fact that matching is done for each side separately (i.e. Tec tracks in the south side are being matched only to Pc clusters in the south side). However, some Tec tracks in one side are projected to the other side. The plot below was made for 2000 events from run # 5895, and one can see that there are more matches for red histogram (**Pc3 Z coordinate flipped**) than for the blue histogram (**Pc3 Y coordinate flipped**). From this histogram one can estimate that ~5% off efficiency is lost due to projection to the same side only.

Pc1 matching

Tec/Pc1 matching works worse, accidentals rate is higher.
The plot below was made for all events in run # 4443.

Correlation between number of Tec tracks and Pc clusters

Following two plots show correlation between the number of Tec tracks and the number of clusters in Pc1 and Pc3 in run # 4443. Only south sides of sectors 1 and 2 were used in these plots.

Tec/Pc3 matching in magnetic field

Tec/Pc matching works equally well for the runs with magnetic field. Event display below was made for event # 18 of run # 7705.

Space resolution with magnetic field.

The following plot was made for 500 events in run # 7705. Both sides of sectors 1 and 2 were used.

Survey geometry was used for both Tec and Pad chambers.

The black histogram shows distance between Pc3 clusters and Tec tracks projected to Pc3. Red and blue histograms show background, calculated by flipping Pc3 Z coordinate or flipping Pc3 Y coordinate.

The space resolution is about 7mm, and is the same as in the case of no magnetic field. But it looks like there is a 0.15 cm systematic shift.

Matching efficiency in magnetic field.

Average (over all multiplicities) Tec/PC3 matching efficiency is shown below as a function of number of Tec hits associated with Tec track for run # 7705. By increasing the cut on number of hits associated with a track, it is possible to reject "ghost" tracks in Tec. As expected, increasing this cut increases matching efficiency.

Average matching efficiency is the same as in the absence of the magnetic field.

Matching efficiency as a function of Tec multiplicity.

The plot below shows Tec/PC3 matching efficiency for two different Tec multiplicities (run # 7705). For low multiplicity events, and tracks with large number of hits, matching efficiency is 85%, which is close to a maximum matching efficiency we should expect (we lose 4-5% due to matching for north and south sides separately and 8-9% due to dead areas in Pc3).

Conclusions

- Tec/Pc3 matching works equally well both with and without magnetic field. Relative space resolution and matching efficiencies are the same.
- Relative space resolution of Tec and Pc3 is about 7mm, which is, in fact, space resolution of Pc3.
- Tec/Pc3 matching efficiency depends on multiplicity. It is 85% for low multiplicity, and 75% for high multiplicity events.
- Tec/Pc1 matching works much worse, relative space resolution is 2-3 times worse, matching efficiency is lower, and there are more accidental matchings. This is probably due to multiple scattering of charged particles between Pc1 and Tec.

Last updated 08/11/00 by [Sasha Lebedev](#)

ZDC Determination of Centrality

I. Method and Simulations:

There are several potential advantages to determining event centrality from spectator multiplicity in the forward direction. For example, the beam fragmentation region has no overlap with the central region in which we measure E_t and $dN^{ch}/d\eta$. In order to justify using ZDC energy to measure event centrality, we model the observed forward energy spectrum- in analogy to what's been done for fixed target experiments in the past.

Our situation is different from fixed target experiments, in which the zero degree calorimeters have measured total "spectator" energy at beam rapidity. In that case the participant number was directly measured. We will apply correction for the fraction of spectator energy in the form of free neutrons and use SPS data to calculate the correction. As a result of this investigation we find that the RHIC ZDC's can also be used to measure centrality but with some restriction in range.

Figure 1: NA49 measurement of spectator Energy (vertical scale) vs, E_t .

NA49 measured both full spectator energy and the "free neutron" spectators as a function of event E_t . Their E_t bins were also labelled with impact parameter, b , using the event simulator "VENUS". They find that E^n/E^{all} is $\sim 1/2$ for the most central collisions and decreases to $1/3$ in the most peripheral collisions. Their neutron data extend to $b < 9$.

Knowing the ratio E^n/E^{all} and making the assumption that it is the same for Au-Au collisions at $\sqrt{s}=130$ AGeV as for Pb-Pb collisions at SPS, we calculate the total spectator number for a given number of observed neutron spectators in a PHENIX event and $N_{participant} = 2 * 197 - N_{spectator}$.

In practice, we use an event generator, JAM (which reproduces the NA49 measurements) to do this calculation, taking into account corrections for neutrons which miss the ZDC (acceptance) and the energy spread due to resolution (based on test beam results) and fermi motion.

We use a BBC multiplicity cut to remove the most peripheral class of events for which we cannot depend on a parametrization of the NA49 data to predict zdc spectra.

As a final check we compare the cross section weighted ZDC spectrum predicted by simulation with the measured spectrum. This is an independent check on the $N_{spectator}$ scale since the spectrum is predicted by geometrical considerations (Glauber model) independent of the NA49 data.

II. Jam Simulation:

The JAM simulation package calculates the fraction of spectator energy carried by neutrons, protons and heavier fragments (deuterons) through a coalescence algorithm. Fig. 2 shows a comparison of JAM with NA49 data.

At RHIC, with an energy of $\sqrt{s}=130$ A GeV, neutrons undergo momentum smearing and have an angular divergence due to fermi motion. The x-distribution of neutrons at the zdc location is shown in fig.3.

The distribution is gaussian and extends beyond the transverse size of the zdc (± 5 cm). The broader component in this distribution arises from low energy, "participant" neutrons and is a minor contributor to the ZDC energy.

The PHENIX ZDC response is computed taking into account the following effects:

1. neutrons must impact the ZDC at ± 4.5 cm. in both x&y.

2. The Testbeam measured response map is applied to obtain signal amplitude
3. Energy is also smeared according to the testbeam measured resolution extrapolated to our (lower) beam energy to give 27% σ/E .

Figure 2. Jam Comparison with NA49 data.

The resulting correction reduces the neutron "true" spectator energy by a factor of 1/1.4 .

The relation $E_{\text{true}}^n/E_{\text{measured}}^n$ is plotted in figure 4 for different

bins of E^n_{measured} .

Figure 3. Calculated distribution of neutrons at the zdc location.

Figure 4. "true" spectator neutrons vs. simulated ZDC observed spectrum

Having determined the neutron spectator multiplicity and using NA49 as a guide, we then calculate the total participant number for each value of measured ZDC multiplicity (fig. 5).

Figure 5. Calculated Participants for 2 values of σ 's in Glauber weights.

In what follows, we use the measured ZDC spectrum as well as BBC multiplicity to determine the range of validity of Fig.5 .

III.Data:

The data sample we use is ZDC*BBLL1 triggers from runs 12127 and 12134 in which B=0 and the ZDC's were operated at a 1.25pC gain setting ($\frac{1}{2}$ the nominal value used for most of this year's run). The ZDC energy calibration is described elsewhere(ref.1). A preliminary conclusion is that PMT response non-linearities were negligible at the nominal gain setting and the conclusions described herein apply equally to the 3 zdc operating gains (2.5, 1.5 and 1.25 pC). We return to this in a later note.

During the same runs we recorded minimum bias ZDC coincidence triggers with a prescale of 60. Since we recorded 2077 events during these 2 runs, we calculate that the Luminosity for these data is given by

$$L \cdot \sigma = 60 \cdot 2077 = 124620$$

and use the calculated ZDC effective cross section (ref.2) of 10.75b corrected to 130AGeV cms energy. Having determined L, we can then calculate effective cross sections for different subset classes selected on ZDC energy. Also of interest is the fraction:

$$(BLL1 \cdot ZDC) / ZDC = 76591 / 124620 = 61.5\%$$

Since the calculated ZDC cross section is 10.75 barns, we obtain:

$$\sigma(BLL1 \cdot ZDC) = 6.6 \text{ b.}$$

which we identify with the Geometrical cross section reduced by BBC acceptance. We use this below to relate to the Glauber model spectrum.

IV. BBC multiplicity:

The total BBC multiplicity (measured by the ADC sums) is plotted vs. ZDC energy in figure 6. The ZDC energy is plotted in multiples of the

Figure 6. BB multiplicity vs. ZDC showing location of cuts in fig. 7

observed single neutron peak energy and summed for both North and South ZDC's (ie total neutron multiplicity).

We see that BBC multiplicity and ZDC energy are anti-correlated for more central collisions, for which the JAM description of ZDC energy is applicable (ie has been compared with SPS data). It is also clear that JAM incorrectly describes the neutron multiplicity for large impact parameters since figure 6 implies that neutron multiplicity decreases with impact parameter for the most peripheral collisions. This is clearly not the case in figure 2.

Figures 7&8. ZDC spectrum with different BBC cuts and simulation.

We then impose further cuts at 2 different levels in BBC multiplicity ($Q > 150k$ and $250k$ channels) and plot the corresponding ZDC spectra in Figure 7.

While the upper bins in ZDC energy are affected by this cut, the bins below 30 are unchanged by the cut. We conclude that these bins have no contamination from peripheral collisions and the JAM prescription is applicable.

Using Figure 5 as a reference, we find that ZDC energy of 30(*65GeV) corresponds to 230 participants or $b=5$, where JAM still agrees well with the NA49 data.

V. Centrality from Cross Sections:

In the central region, corresponding to $N_{\text{participant}} > 230$, both ZDC energy and cross section should increase monotonically with impact parameter. The distribution in $N_{\text{participant}}$ was calculated using Glauber weights with $\sigma_{\text{NN}}^{\text{inelastic}} = 39$ mb. and the predicted zdc spectrum relies on the Jam parametrization of fragmentation into unbound neutrons shown in Figure 2.

There is a clear discrepancy between fragmentation as modeled by JAM, which predicts that neutron multiplicity (ZDC energy) grows monotonically with impact parameter, and our data (figs. 6 & 7) which shows that the ZDC energy eventually falls for the most peripheral bins. The origin of this discrepancy is the coalescence method used in JAM to determine the fraction of unbound spectator neutrons. So far as we know, there is no event generator which satisfactorily describes the fragmentation for the peripheral collisions accessed with the PHENIX ZDC's. This is clearly an area for future work.

In spite of this discrepancy, it is interesting to compare our measured distribution with JAM for the most central events where we fit the NA49 data points. In this region we expect the differential cross section to agree with our data.

We find 14033 events in the region, $ZDC < 30$ neutrons, compared with a calculated total zdc trigger sample of $N_{\text{zdc}} = 124620$ events (=10.75 barns). So the actual data in our $N_{\text{participant}} > 230$ range is $14033/124620 * 10.75 = 1.20$ barns or 17.2% of the geometrical cross section (7 Barns).

We computed simulated ZDC distributions using JAM, with appropriate cross section weighting. Events were generated with impact

parameters 0-12 fermi and 0-18 fermi using a Woods-Saxon profile and an NN inelastic cross section of 39 mbarns. As expected, the two samples have a relative population of 4.5 b/7 b corresponding to the fraction of the geometrical cross section with $b < 12$ fermi.

We then compare cross sections for the bins 0-25 neutrons and 0-30 neutrons with the data plotted in Fig. 7.

Using the Jam simulation we calculate .80 and .97 barns for the integrated cross sections over the 2 intervals, respectively. In the data we find 10301 events and 14,033 events in the corresponding bins and with the Luminosity derived above we find .88 and 1.2 barns. The statistical errors from simulation are of order 9%. Perhaps more significantly, the systematic errors on the NA49 data on which we base our comparison are quoted as +/-20% in ref.3.

So, our conclusion is that JAM underpredicts the ZDC energy differential cross section in the $M_{\text{neutron}} < 30$ region at the level of 20%. The discrepancy with the SPS data on which we base simulation is probably within quoted systematic errors. The Jam predicted spectrum and our data are directly compared in Fig.8, where we see that the shape of the spectrum is reasonably well fit by the simulation.

Judging from figure 7, the ZDC's provide a useful centrality determination when combined with a minimal BBC multiplicity cut so long as the measured multiplicity is <30-40 neutrons.

References:

- 1) Technical Note on Determining the ZDC Energy Scale, M.Chiu et al
- 2) NIM A417 p. 1 ('98)
- 3) "Jam"- Yasushi Nara. Nucl.Phys.A638, 555c,1998; nucl-th/9802016
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Analysis Note 015 - September 26, 2000

Minimum Bias Triggers and Offline Vertex Determination at PHENIX

L. Ewell

Abstract

The purpose of this note is to address the problem of offline vertex determination using the Beam Beam Counter (BBC) and Zero Degree Calorimeter (ZDC) minimum bias trigger detectors of PHENIX. The energy dependence on the ZDCs and slewing corrections will also be considered.

Determination of the Z vertex of the collision point at PHENIX is a quantity of interest. The note by H. Ohnishi [2](#) that concerned a pre Si shutdown run was a good starting point in this area. In addition, the note by C. Maguire [3](#) also provided insight into this area, particularly with respect to the Pad Chamber subsystem.

The BBC and ZDC both detect collision fragments/particles that are emitted at forward pseudorapidities (η). The BBC covers a more central region ($3.0 < \eta < 3.9$) symmetric around $z = 0$. It also covers the full azimuth and is sensitive to the Cerenkov radiation of charged

particles [4](#). The ZDC is located at a more forward η ([6](#)) and is sensitive to the neutral particles that do not get deflected by the Dx sweeping magnets [5](#).

Throughout the run during the summer of 2000, a 'minimum bias' trigger was used to acquire most of the data that was taken at PHENIX. It is not the intent of this note to discuss the electronics and trigger logic that was involved in this. For this information, the reader is referred to the informative web page of Iowa State/Ames laboratory that describes this [6](#). However, at a basic level the minimum bias trigger can be thought of as the logical OR of a coincidence between the north and south ZDC (ZDC_N&&ZDC_S) and the north and south Beam Beam Counters (Beam Beam Local Level 1 (BBLL1)).

In the course of the summer, it was found out that this 'minimum bias' trigger had a substantial component (≈ 4 barns out of a total of 10.7) of mutual Electromagnetic Dissociation (ED) of the beam nuclei which resulted in a single neutron in each arm. These events deposited very little energy into the EM Cal. Due to limited bandwidth of the daq, the ZDC trigger was consequently prescaled by factors ranging from 2 to 60.

The note by S. Belikov describes the bit patterns of the different triggers [7](#). In Figure 1, we see a histogram of the trigger distribution for run 11014 which started at 4:42 on 8/20/00. We see that as a

result of the prescaling, the triggers that were accepted were dominated by the ZDC AND BLL1 (trigger bit $0x4000 + 0x1000 + 0x2(\text{prescaled}) = 0x5000$ (or $0x5002$) = 20480 (or 20482) decimal).

Figure 1: Trigger Distribution for run 11014

It is instructive to plot the charge that the BBC sees vs the energy that the ZDC sees. In Figure 2., we see this plotted with the green points representing the ZDC AND LL1, the blue points representing the ZDCs and the red points representing the BLL1s. In this picture, it is important to remember that the red dots are plotted on top of the blue dots which are in turn plotted on top of the green dots.

Figure 2: BBC Charge vs ZDC Energy for run 11014. Green - ZDC AND BBL1, BLUE ZDC and RED BBL1

To determine the Z-vertex offline, the time that each detector fired needs to be known. The BBC was designed to have a timing resolution of ≈ 50 ps corresponding to a distance of ≈ 1.5 cm. The ZDC was designed to have a slightly lower resolution of ≈ 150 ps. The z vertex is determined via

$$Z_{vertex} = c * (Time_S - Time_N)/2.0$$

where c is the speed of light. In Figure 3., we see the z vertices as determined by the BBC and the ZDC. In the ZDC picture, we can see the steep edges that occur around the ± 60 cm from the BBC z vertex.

Figure 3: BBC and ZDC Vertices for run 11014

Since there is a distribution of energies in the ZDC that corresponds to different event centralities, it is worthwhile to investigate the dependence of the Z -vertex on the amount of energy that a given event deposits in the ZDC. In Figure 4., we see the difference of the BBC vertex and the ZDC vertex. 67

Figure 4: Difference of BBC and ZDC Vertex for run 11014

The fact that the peak is centered at zero shows the timing consistency between the two detectors. The RMS value of 5.3 cm reflects an upper value for the timing resolution.

In figure 5, we see the same plot with cuts on ZDC energy.

Figure 5: Vertex dependence on ZDC Energy for run 11014

We see that the resolution increases with ZDC energy. This may be correlated with the larger signals that higher energy events deposit in the ZDC.

It should be pointed out that corrections, in particular slewing corrections, play a large role in determining the timing resolution of both the BBC and ZDC detectors. The ZDC slewing corrections were determined by M. Chiu [8](#).

The ZDC slew corrected time is determined via

$$T_{cor} = T - \left(T_0 + \frac{S_1}{ADC + S_2} + \frac{S_3}{ADC + S_4} \right).$$

From this relationship, one can see that low energy events have higher slewing corrections. The BBC slow corrected time is determined differently 1.

Figure 6: Vertex dependence with no ZDC slewing corrections

In Figure 6, we see the ZDC energy dependence of the Z vertex with no ZDC slewing corrections. We see that, as expected, the low energy events are affected more. The resolution is degraded. In addition, we

see a time offset that is less dependent on energy.

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Analysis Note 018 - September 27, 2000

Determining the Number of Participants Using a Hybrid Glauber Model Approach

Mickey Chiu, Saskia Mioduszewski, Dave Morrison, Jamie Nagle, Klaus Reygers

Introduction

This note describes a technique for using a Glauber model to estimate the number of participants (also, wounded nucleons) in a heavy-ion collision. The basic technique is to make cuts on an observable to define classes of events and then look to corresponding classes of events in the distribution of $d\sigma/dN_{part}$ versus

N_{part} in the Glauber model. The average number of participants can then be determined directly from the model. The observable used to define the experimental event classes needs to be a monotonic function of impact parameter, b , *on average*. Fluctuations in the value of the observable about its average affect the determination of the number of participants. The effect of fluctuations can be estimated from the data themselves or by using a model such as HIJING.

What is the Physics?

Essentially all models of heavy ion collisions assume a monotonic relation between the number of participating nucleons (N_p) and the charged particle multiplicity ($dN_{ch}/d\eta$). This assumption is true on-average, but does not hold event-by-event due to fluctuations between the two quantities. Thus for the event averaged quantities one can always write this monotonic relation in the form:

$$dN_{ch}/d\eta = C_1 \times N_p^{\alpha_1} + C_2 \times N_p^{\alpha_2} + \dots \quad (1)$$

Figure: $dN_{ch}/d\eta$ per participant nucleon pair versus N_p for different physics models. The blue curve in HIJING. The red point in the PHOBOS data point.

2000/08/30 08.59

In a recent paper by Wang and Gyulassy they make a plot of $dN_{ch}/d\eta$ per participant pair versus N_p [2]. I have reproduced this plot as shown in figure 1. The blue line is the results from the HIJING model and follows the monotonic relation:

$$dN_{ch}/d\eta = 0.95 \times N_p^{1.0} + 0.00163 \times N_p^{2.0} \quad (2)$$

One can think of this in HIJING as contributions from soft (first term) and hard (second term) components. They also show a curve representing the saturation model of Eskola (which is reproduced with the curve labeled $\alpha = 0.9$). All the models converge at the same value for the most central collisions (as now constrained by the PHOBOS data point seen on the plot []).

Their call is to measure more data points over a range in N_p to discriminate between these models. This is identically the same thing as determining the on average monotonic relationship between $dN_{ch}/d\eta$ and N_p .

Glauber Model Basics

A Glauber model provides a simple way to describe a high-energy collision of two nuclei. Such a model does not describe the dynamics of the collision; therefore, there are limits on the type of questions that can be addressed using a Glauber model. The model calculates the thickness of nuclear matter in the direct path of each oncoming nucleon and uses the nucleon-nucleon inelastic cross section (σ_{nn}^{inel}) to decide whether a nucleon-nucleon collision has occurred. By integrating this procedure over the full distribution of nucleons in each nucleus, one can determine the number of struck nucleons.

A Glauber model depends on a few simple assumptions. One, that nucleons of one nucleus travel in straight line trajectories as they pass through the other nucleus. Also, that the basic nucleon-nucleon cross sections don't change during the course of the collision. Both of these assumptions are reasonable for high-energy nucleus-nucleus collisions.

It's important to use a realistic density profile for the nuclei. The usual approach is to use a Woods-Saxon density profile with suitably chosen parameters

$$\rho(r) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp \frac{r-r_n}{d}} \quad (3)$$

We have taken values for the parameters from deJager [1]

$$r_n = 1.19 A^{1/3} - 1.61 A^{-1/3} \quad (4)$$

$$A = 197 \quad (5)$$

$$d = 0.54 \quad (6)$$

The following plot shows the dependence of the nucleus-nucleus total cross section, σ_{NN}^{tot} , on the diffuseness parameter, d .

Figure: σ_{NN}^{tot} as a function of nuclear diffuseness

One also needs to specify the inelastic nucleon-nucleon cross section, σ_{nn}^{inel} . At the lower energies of the AGS and SPS, it's pretty typical to see value of 30mb used. Of course, there's an energy dependence to this cross section, and at $\sqrt{s} = 130$ A GeV, the value is closer to 40mb. The following plot shows the effect on the total nucleus-nucleus cross section if one varies σ_{nn}^{inel}

Figure: σ_{NN}^{tot} as a function of σ_{nn}^{inel}

Figure 4: Glauber Model event distribution of number of participating nucleons

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Different Monotonic Parameterizations

For this specific model study we will restrict ourselves to monotonic relations of the form:

$$dN_{char}/d\eta = C_1 \times N_p^\alpha \quad (7)$$

Thus there are three parameters available. They are C_1 , α , and a total normalization value. In addition one needs to model the event-by-event fluctuations that lead to specific event deviations from this monotonic relation. These fluctuations play an important role in extracting the true average relation.

In this study, we have assumed only binomial statistical fluctuations. This assumption can be tested by

comparing the track number difference distribution event-by-event from one half of the Pad Chamber and the other half (Klaus' suggestion). Since the Pad Chamber uncorrected multiplicity distribution is the result of a signal and then background subtraction, the below described modeling of the fluctuations is not precise.

Functionally what is done is in the following code:

```
for( $i = 1; i < N_p^\alpha; i++$ )
```

```
if( $random < C_1$ )  $nch++$ ;
```

More thought certainly needs to go into this part.

We have simulated 100,000 events for different values of α that span the range of physics predictions for the monotonic relationship. For each value of α we select the C_1 value that gives the best fit to the shoulder of the PHENIX data multiplicity distribution. Shown in the following plots (figures 3-6) are the distributions as calculated in this Glauber model (blue histograms). The black histograms are the same thing with more coarse binning, which some people prefer. The red points are the "NOT FINAL" (and approximate) PHENIX data points.

Figure: Model of uncorrected charged particle multiplicity. The histograms are the model with $\alpha = 0.9$. The model is normalized to agree with the data at an x-axis value of 52.5.

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Figure: Model of uncorrected charged particle multiplicity. The histograms are the model with $\alpha = 1.1$. The model is normalized to agree with the data at an x-axis value of 52.5.

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Figure: Model of uncorrected charged particle multiplicity. The histograms are the model with $\alpha = 1.5$. The model is normalized to agree with the data at an x-axis value of 52.5.

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Figure: Model of uncorrected charged particle multiplicity. The histograms are the model with $\alpha = 3.0$. The model is normalized to agree with the data at an x-axis value of 52.5.

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For this set of plots the normalization is determined so that the data and model agree at a value of 52.5 on the x-axis.

Sensitivity of Total Integral and Shape

One can see that the shape (on this log scale) looks the same in the flat and shoulder region for almost all values of the α parameter. However, the distributions disagree quite significantly for the more peripheral events. As the α is increased, the peak on the left increases quite dramatically.

Terry has suggested there could be differences not so easily seen, so we have fit a simple exponential to the range of charge particle multiplicities from 20.0 to 50.0. We find there is a dependence in the slope on the α parameter as shown in figure 7.

Figure: Exponential fit slope parameter (from multiplicity range 20-50) as a function of α .

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Maybe this feature can be exploited to constrain the models as well when comparing to the final PHENIX data result.

We then plot the relative difference between the integral of the data histogram and the integral of the model histogram (see figure 8). This is really asking if the model is normalized to agree with the flat section and shoulder, does it agree with the correct total cross section (or integral) of the data. In this study, we have assumed that the data represents 100% of the total Au + Au inelastic cross section, and has no background contribution. If this is not true, that can be accounted for and should not be a major problem in the case where it is 96% over the cross section with a 2% error (just as an example).

Figure 10: The relative error difference between the integral of the data and the integral of the model (if we normalize the model with agree with the data at the point $x = 52.5$).

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It appears by this method that only certain values of α can give a consistent agreement with the integral (total cross section) and the full shape. In this case, it would indicate a monotonic relation with an α value of approximately 1.6 with a guess-estimate error of 0.3. NOTE THAT THIS IS NOT THE FINAL ANSWER SINCE WE ARE TESTING THE MODEL ON NOT FINAL PHENIX DATA. ESPECIALLY IF THE TRIGGER INFORMATION IS NOT USED CORRECTLY IT COULD REALLY CHANGE THE ANSWER.

Normalizing in a Different Way

One may prefer an alternative method, in which the model has the normalization fixed to match the data's total integral. This means requiring that the model be consistent with the total cross section. Then the previously plotted model-data comparisons look as follows (figures 9-12):

Figure: Model of uncorrected charged particle multiplicity. The histograms are the model with $\alpha = 0.9$. The model is normalized to agree with the total integral of the data.

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Figure: Model of uncorrected charged particle multiplicity. The histograms are the model with $\alpha = 1.1$. The model is normalized to agree with the total integral of the data.

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Figure: Model of uncorrected charged particle multiplicity. The histograms are the model with $\alpha = 1.5$. The model is normalized to agree with the total integral of the data.

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Figure: Model of uncorrected charged particle multiplicity. The histograms are the model with $\alpha = 3.0$. The model is normalized to agree with the total integral of the data.

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One can now ask which values of α agree with the distribution and one again converges on the same α value of 1.6. This is natural because the two pictures are really asking for consistency between the model and the data for both the total cross section and the shape simultaneously.

Extracting N_p Values

If one believes that one has a constrained monotonic relation, then for that α parameter model we can make cuts on the observed charged particle multiplicity. We have made cuts that are shown as arrows on the multiplicity figures and they correspond to (bin D) 0-5% most central events, (bin C) 5-15%, (bin B) 15-33%, and (bin A) 33-100% of the total inelastic cross section. One can apply these hard cuts on the charged particle multiplicity in the model and then plot the distributions for N_p for each of the four selections. These four distributions are shown for a given $\alpha = 1.5$ model in figure 13.

Figure 15: Distribution of participants for four different cuts on the charged particle multiplicity within the model.

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Below we show the N_p mean values for these four bins for all of the different models using different values of α . These will obviously span the full range of physics scenarios. Thus, it is the essential physics point to be able to select a unique α value (at least with some reasonably small systematic error).

Figure: Number of participants in each bin as a function of α

α	Bin A	Bin B	Bin C	Bin D
0.9	19	104	221	320
1.0	22	117	232	322
1.1	25	128	241	325
1.3	32	152	260	333
1.5	37	169	212	337
1.7	42	186	284	342
1.9	46	200	290	344
2.0	47	205	293	345
3.0	61	249	317	354

If (and this is a big if) one believes the model is constrained (for example) to be α is between 1.3 and 1.9, then one gets a range of systematic errors for the N_p for each bin. It is clear that the most peripheral bin (A) has by far the most model dependent.

How to be confident about the results

This is up for discussion. Certainly having a confirming set of participant estimates from the ZDC analysis for at least the three more central bins would help. There was also the suggested study (from Klaus) to confirm the model of the fluctuations.

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About this document ...

Determining the Number of Participants Using a Hybrid Glauber Model Approach

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PHENIX INTERNAL ANALYSIS NOTE

Analysis Note 019 - August 18, 2000

Analysis Note

"Multiplicity Measurements with the PHENIX Drift Chamber"

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SUNY Stony Brook, September 26, 2000

Introduction

This note describes the analysis performed to extract the multiplicity distribution of primary charged particles from tracks reconstructed with the PHENIX drift chambers (DC).

For the moment we restrict the analysis to minimum bias data for Au + Au collisions at $\sqrt{s}/NN = 130$ GeV measured in the nominal (not-retracted) detector geometry without magnetic field in the central arms of the experiment.

Analysis framework

The analysis is based on 29 files of the runs 10545 - 10708.

For the reconstruction of tracks in the drift chamber the current default version (Candidatory version 1.19, repository tag phs5) of the pattern recognition and tracking code was used. In this framework tracks are reconstructed in the xy-plane by using the hits recorded in the X1 and X2 wire nets of the drift chambers. No information from hits in UV wire nets is taken into account in our analysis and, therefore, our analysis is done entirely with the projections of all reconstructed tracks into the xy plane.

The beam-beam counter (BBC) measures the z coordinate of the collision vertex. For the BBC analysis we use the current default version (repository tag phs5).

Event selection

All hardware triggers, except laser and test-pulsar triggers, were accepted for the analysis.

Events are selected according to the vertex z coordinate reconstructed with the BBC as shown in Fig. 1. Events with $|z_{\text{BBC}}^{\text{BBC}}| < 30\text{cm}$ have been accepted for further analysis. A more stringent cut would be desirable but requires a larger data sample.

The cut on $|z_{\text{vtx}}^{\text{BBC}}| < 30\text{cm}$ reduces the available statistics from 19178 to 14598 events.

No further event selection cuts are applied.

Track selection

The correlation between the track multiplicities measured in the east and west drift chambers before applying any track selection cuts is shown in Fig. 2. The profile histogram drawn as an overlay to the scatter plot has been fitted with a straight line. The multiplicities are proportional to each other. It is obvious, however, that in DC east fewer tracks are reconstructed compared to DC west. This reflects the reduced overall performance of DC east due to not fully operational wire nets. Fig. 3 shows the resulting total multiplicity distribution. This distribution includes not only tracks from primary particles from the collision vertex but has also significant contributions from particle decays in flight and especially from particles scattered from or created by secondary interactions (albedo) in PHENIX material as the magnet steel. The latter contribution corresponds to about half of the tracks reconstructed in the drift chambers.

In order to reduce the contributions from non-primary particles we make use of the fact that particles originating from the collision vertex point back to this point in the xy plane. In order to cut on the minimum distance of a track from the vertex in the xy plane it is first necessary to reconstruct the vertex coordinates. This can be achieved using tracks reconstructed in the two drift chambers as demonstrated in Fig. 4. Since the detector alignment is not yet perfect the vertex reconstruction has to be done separately for both drift chambers. Due to the PHENIX geometry the vertex resolution in y is significantly better than in x. Furthermore, the vertex resolution achieved for DC west is better than for DC east since on average more tracks contribute to the event-by-event vertex fit in DC west.

For each reconstructed track we calculate the minimum distance to the average collision vertex in the xy plane determined for DC east or DC west, respectively. The resulting transverse-distance distribution is shown in Fig. 5. In order to reduce contributions from tracks not originating from the collision vertex we select those tracks with a transverse distance below 5 cm for further analysis. Obviously, a fraction of the tracks pointing back to the collision vertex in the xy plane is still due to albedo. Correcting for that contribution will be a central issue for the remaining analysis.

Fig. 6 demonstrates that, after this cut on the pointing back to the collision vertex, the multiplicities of tracks reconstructed in DC east and DC west remain proportional to each other. The uncorrected total number of reconstructed tracks after the vertex cut is shown in Fig. 7. The cut reduces the track multiplicities by $\approx 45\%$.

Corrections

Geometrical acceptance and detector efficiency

The correction for the acceptance of the drift chambers in azimuth and pseudo rapidity is straight forward.

Fig. 8 shows the azimuthal distribution of tracks pointing to the vertex for DC west and DC east.

The angular range covered corresponds to 3.02 rad. We estimate a systematic error of 0.04 rad based on the bin width of the distribution. Therefore, the resulting correction for azimuthal coverage is given by:

$$\epsilon_{\Delta\phi} = (3.02 \pm 0.04)/2\pi = 0.48 \pm 0.006 \quad (1)$$

To determine the coverage in pseudo rapidity η we can not use the measured data, since z information is not taken into account in the present analysis and, consequently, the pseudo rapidity is not measured. Instead, we extract the coverage from a PISA simulation of 750 min. bias Au + Au collisions taking the proper detector geometry into account. Fig. 9 shows the resulting η distribution. The minimum and maximum pseudo rapidity covered by the detector acceptance depends on the vertex position in z , while the width $\Delta\eta$ of the covered interval is almost independent on the z coordinate of the vertex. It can be shown analytically that $\Delta\eta$ changes by less than 2% if one varies the z coordinate of the vertex between 0 cm and 40 cm. In order to be able to directly read off the pseudo rapidity coverage from the η distribution we therefore in the simulation select events with a collision vertex close to $z = 0$ cm.

In Fig.9 we show the η distributions of particles from collisions occurring within ± 5 cm and ± 2 cm, respectively, to demonstrate via Monte Carlo the acceptance of the drift chambers in η . Within the statistical accuracy both distributions cover pseudo rapidities from -0.4 to $+0.4$ and do not show a significant dependence on the selected window in the z coordinate of the collision vertex. To correct the measured multiplicity distribution for a pseudo-rapidity coverage of 1 unit we therefore apply the following correction:

$$\epsilon_{\Delta\eta} = (0.80 \pm 0.02) \quad (2)$$

The correction for inefficient and non-operational detector regions is based on the azimuthal distributions of tracks as shown in Fig. 8. As we pointed out already earlier, a large fraction of wire nets in DC east could not be operated properly while the situation is much better, though not perfect, for DC west. Certain regions in DC west, however, are known to perform according to the nominal specifications. Especially, for $\phi < -0.35$ rad and around

$\phi = 0.3$ rad DC west is highly efficient. Those regions were used to provide reference values for the number of reconstructed tracks per angle bin. The reference value of 6600 ± 100 entries per bin is indicated by the horizontal lines in Fig. 8. Average correction factors for the individual drift chambers are then calculated by dividing the total number of tracks in DC west and DC east, respectively, by the expected number of tracks given by the reference value per bin and the width of the interval covered in ϕ . The corrections are:

$$\epsilon_{DC}^{\text{west}} = (0.85 \pm 0.02) \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon_{DC}^{\text{east}} = (0.55 \pm 0.01) \quad (4)$$

Tracking efficiency

The track reconstruction efficiency in the xy plane is high. From eye scans of ≈ 100 events on the DC event display the efficiency has been estimated to exceed 90 %. For the present analysis, we evaluated the performance of the track reconstruction in a Monte Carlo procedure. We simulated 750 min. bias Au + Au collisions from HIJING with PISA, using a flat distribution of the collision vertex between -30 cm and +30 cm. Subsequently, we ran the full response and reconstruction chains for the simulated data.

In this Monte Carlo approach we want to address two questions:

- What is the overall track reconstruction efficiency and how does it depend on the multiplicity of reconstructed tracks?
- How can we deal with multiple reconstruction of a single track (ghosts) and subtract the ghost tracks from the measured multiplicities?

To calculate these corrections we use the DC evaluation. Based on a dominant contributor analysis, it is straightforward to determine the fraction of Monte Carlo tracks which have been reconstructed by the DC pattern recognition. The upper curve in Fig. 10 shows the resulting reconstruction efficiency as a function of the multiplicity of reconstructed tracks. The average efficiency of about 90% is consistent with the values obtained from the eye scan. With increasing track multiplicity the reconstruction efficiency decreases as one would expect. The drop in efficiency at the lowest bins is an artefact of the fact that the efficiency and multiplicity are correlated: by definition the reconstruction efficiency is zero for zero reconstructed tracks.

By a variation of the intrinsic resolution and other parameters which go into the simulation of the DC response we can determine the systematic error in the procedure. As a conservative estimate, we presently take a relative systematic error of $0.06/0.90 = 0.067$ for the tracking efficiency into account.

Multiple reconstruction of tracks is likely for tracks passing the DC through the proportional region of the drift cells since there the left-right ambiguity can not be resolved. On the contrary, for tracks passing the DC through the drift region of the individual cells this ambiguity is avoided by gate and back-drift wires which assure that tracks are registered only on one side of the wire.

The description of the signal generation in the proportional region is difficult in the Monte Carlo but essential for a quantitative estimate of the number of ghost tracks. So far, only a qualitative agreement of data and Monte Carlo has been achieved. Therefore, we exclude all tracks which pass the DC through the proportional region of the drift cells from our analysis. This cut is, to first order, purely geometrical in nature and can be corrected for without detailed simulation of the field configuration and charge collection on the anode wires.

Fig. 11 shows the average drift distance for tracks pointing to the vertex. For perfect track reconstruction one would expect the drift-distance distribution to be flat. Obviously, in the proportional region, which corresponds to drift distances smaller than 0.3 cm, a significant excess of tracks is reconstructed which indicates multiple track reconstruction. Also at large drift distances some excess is visible which, however, is small compared to the excess in the proportional region. This may be attributed to tracks crossing from one drift cell into the neighboring one which can lead to multiple reconstruction of the track if the two resulting track segments are slightly displaced due to possible deviation from the perfect detector geometry.

In order to eliminate the ghost problem we remove all tracks from our sample which fall into the proportional region. In the Monte Carlo simulation we then can calculate the remaining contribution of ghost tracks outside of the proportional region where the response simulation is less difficult. Fig. 12 shows that after excluding the proportional region almost no ghost tracks remain. No dependence on the multiplicity of reconstructed tracks is observed within the statistics available.

Consequently, the reconstruction efficiency has to be recalculated taking this cut into account. The lower curve in Fig. 11 shows the resulting reconstruction efficiency which decreases according to the effective loss in distance coverage. Within the statistics available the multiplicity dependence remains unchanged.

In summary, the following corrections are applied to the reconstructed multiplicities M_{track} in order to correct for

tracking efficiency and ghost track contributions:

$$\epsilon_{track} = 0.79 - 0.0002 \times M_{track} \quad (5)$$

$$\epsilon_{ghost} = 0.99 \quad (6)$$

For the relative systematic errors we estimate 6.7% for ϵ_{track} (see above) and 1% for ϵ_{ghost}

Correction for vertex-pointing cut

To correction for the cut on the minimum transverse distance d_{vtx} of the tracks to the collision vertex has to incorporate two different effects:

1. A fraction of primary particles impinging on the detector is lost by cutting on d_{vtx} because of the limited pointing resolution.
2. A significant fraction of the tracks pointing to the vertex in the xy plane is due to decays and particles not originating from the collision vertex (albedo).

The second effect is clearly the more important one and, unfortunately, subject to quite large systematic uncertainties.

In order to estimate the necessary correction we used our Monte Carlo simulation as described above. The resulting d_{vtx} distributions are shown in Fig. 13. If one compares the Monte Carlo distributions to the measured ones (c.f. Fig. 5) two observations can be made:

1. The pointing resolution in the Monte Carlo is significantly better than seen in the data.
2. The tail towards larger distances appears to be significantly larger relative to the peak at small distances for the data compared to the simulation.

To account for the difference in resolution between data and simulation in first order, we can extract the correction factors for the data (where we cut at $d_{vtx} < 5$ cm) by cutting at a lower value of d_{vtx} in the simulation. In the present analysis, we use $d_{vtx} < 4$ cm as effective cut in the Monte Carlo and estimate the corresponding systematic error by a variation of the d_{vtx} cut by ± 2 cm. In the d_{vtx} range from 2 cm to 6 cm the fraction of primary particles lost by applying the cut ranges from 8.0% (cut at 2 cm) to 2.5% (cut at 6 cm). In the same d_{vtx} range the contribution of non-primary particles to all tracks ranges from 18.5% (cut at 2 cm) to 25.0% (cut at 6 cm). The relative systematic error reflecting the variation of the d_{vtx} cut in the simulation by ± 2 cm corresponds to 7%. This error accounts for the uncertainty in the resolution only.

The contamination of secondary particles either from decays or albedo predicted by the simulation on average is 20%. The comparison between data (Fig. 5) and Monte Carlo (Fig. 13) reveals that the relative contribution of tracks

with large transverse distance to the vertex is larger in the data than in the simulation by about a factor 2. This indicates that the number of secondaries is underestimated in the simulation by a similar amount. In lack of a more precise estimate, at the present stage of the analysis, we correct only for the fraction of secondaries generated in the Monte Carlo simulation. The resulting correction for the cut on d_{vtx} attributes to a correction factor of

$$\epsilon_{vertex} = (1 - 0.209)/0.955 = 0.828 \quad (7)$$

A detailed analysis of the contribution of non-primary particles to our track sample will be the subject of a future analysis note.

Correction for decay in flight of primary particles

The fraction of primary particles which decay in flight before they reach the drift chambers has been determined based on HIJING in a standard way.

Since the path length of the particles from the collision vertex to the drift chambers is known the correction factor only depends on the momentum distribution of the primary particles and the relative intensities of the primary pions, kaons, and protons.

In order to estimate the systematic error of the resulting decay correction the momentum spectra have been scaled by $\pm 20\%$ and the relative contribution of the particle species have been varied by $\pm 30\%$.

The resulting correction factor is given by:

$$\epsilon_{decay} = 0.856 \pm 0.040 \quad (8)$$

This result is consistent with a very simple approximation based on the following ingredients:

- average path length to the drift chamber: 220 cm
- particle species ratio: pion / kaon / proton $\approx 600 / 100 / 60$
- average momentum: 0.5 GeV/c

A back-of-the-envelope calculation of the decay correction yields a correction factor of 86%.

Result

Finally, we apply the corrections outlined above to the multiplicity distribution shown in Fig. 7. The corrected multiplicity M_{corr} is calculated from M_{cut}^{west} and M_{cut}^{east} according to:

$$M_{corr} = (M_{cut}^{west} / \epsilon_{DC}^{west} + M_{cut}^{east} / \epsilon_{DC}^{east}) * (\epsilon_{ghost} / \epsilon_{track}) * (\epsilon_{vertex} / \epsilon_{decay}) / (\epsilon_{\Delta\phi} * \epsilon_{\Delta\eta}) \quad (9)$$

The resulting distribution is shown in Fig. 14.

Due to the underestimate of the albedo contribution the multiplicity is probably overestimated by 15-30 %.

All other systematics errors are summarized in the following:

- $\epsilon_{\Delta\phi}$: 1.3%
- $\epsilon_{\Delta\eta}$: 2.5%
- $\epsilon_{DC}^{\text{west}} + \epsilon_{DC}^{\text{east}}$: 3.5%
- ϵ_{track} : 6.6%
- ϵ_{ghost} : 1.0%
- ϵ_{vertex} : 7.0% (contribution from resolution only)
- ϵ_{decay} : 4.7%

Summing these uncertainties quadratically give a total systematic uncertainty of 11.7%.

Figures

Figure 1: Distribution of the z coordinate of the collision vertex measured with the BBC. The arrows indicate the z range of events accepted for further analysis.

Figure 2: Raw track multiplicity measured in the east DC versus west DC.

Figure 3: Total raw track multiplicity reconstructed in both drift chambers.

Figure 4: Reconstructed x coordinate (upper row) and y coordinate (lower row) of the collision vertex determined with tracks reconstructed in DC east (left) and DC west (right), respectively.

Figure 5: Transverse distance of tracks to the collision vertex (DC east and DC west combined). The upper panel shows the full distribution on a logarithmic scale while the lower panel zooms in to the lowest 10 cm on a linear scale. The arrow indicates the maximum transverse distance of those tracks accepted for further analysis.

Figure 6: Track multiplicity after cutting on the transverse distance to the collision vertex measured in the east DC versus west DC.

Figure 7: Total track multiplicity reconstructed in both drift chambers after cutting on the transverse distance to the collision vertex.

Figure 8: Azimuthal distributions for tracks pointing to the vertex for DC west (upper panel) and DC east (lower panel). The horizontal line at 6600 tracks / 10 mrad defines the level of track reconstruction corresponding to nominal detector efficiency.

Figure 9: Pseudo rapidity distribution of tracks pointing to the collision vertex which has been restricted to absolute values below 5 cm (upper curve) and 2 cm (lower curve), respectively. These distributions were obtained from a PISA simulation of 750 min. bias Au+Au collisions.

Figure 10: Track reconstruction efficiency as function of the multiplicity of reconstructed tracks as calculated from Monte Carlo. For the blue (lower) curve tracks in the proportional region have been rejected while for the red (upper) curve all tracks have been considered.

Figure 11: Distribution of the average drift distance measured in the data for tracks pointing to the vertex. The proportional region of the drift cells corresponds to the region below 0.3 cm.

Figure 12: Number of reconstructed tracks after subtraction of ghost tracks relative to the track multiplicity as function of the latter.

Figure 13: Transverse distance of tracks to the collision vertex (DC east and DC west combined) as calculated in our Monte Carlo simulation. The upper panel shows the full distribution on a logarithmic scale while the lower panel zooms in to the lowest 10 cm on a linear scale.

Figure: Fully corrected preliminary multiplicity distribution for charged particles in min. bias Au +Au collisions at $\sqrt{s}/NN = 130$ GeV.

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Analysis Note 023 - October 2, 2000

``Background Subtraction in the $\frac{dN_{ch}}{d\eta}$ | $\eta=0$ Distribution measured with the PHENIX Drift Chamber''

R. Aeverbeck, A. Drees, J.M. Heuser, J. Jia, F. Messer, F. Muehlbacher
for the PHENIX Collaboration
SUNY Stony Brook, September 29, 2000

Introduction

This note is an addendum to our recently submitted analysis note ([1]) which describes the measurement of the charged particle pseudo-rapidity density at mid rapidity $\frac{dN_{ch}}{d\eta}$ | $\eta=0$ using tracks reconstructed with the PHENIX drift chambers (DC). The analysis is based on minimum bias data for Au + Au collisions at $\sqrt{s}/NN = 130$ GeV measured in the nominal (not retracted) detector geometry without magnetic field in the central arms of the experiment.

As we pointed out in [1], it is of prime importance for the multiplicity analysis to reduce in the data sample the contribution of tracks from non-primary particles, i.e. decay products and albedo, and to apply a proper correction for those non-primary tracks which have not been removed by the track selection cut. Tracks are accepted if their projection into the xy plane points back to the collision vertex (within a distance window of 5 cm), as described in section 4 of Ref. [1]. The correction for this vertex-pointing cut relies on a Monte Carlo simulation of minimum bias Au + Au collisions (see Sec. 5.3 of Ref. [1]).

As will be demonstrated in the following, the background level due to albedo is severely underestimated in our current Monte Carlo simulation. Therefore, the contribution of non-primary tracks to the data sample was underestimated and, accordingly, the value of the correction factor applied to the measured multiplicities was too large.

This has been pointed out already in Ref. [1]. The quantitative analysis of the background contribution was work in progress at that time and has been completed now. In the following, we will present an update of the correction for the vertex-pointing cut based on a proper description of the background in the distribution of the minimum transverse distance of tracks to the collision vertex. Within our systematical error, the resulting distribution of the charged particle pseudo-rapidity density at mid rapidity is consistent with the corresponding result obtained from pad-chamber data (see Ref. [3]).

Non-primary particles: data versus simulation

The following three sections demonstrate the discrepancy between data and simulation concerning the relative contribution of background tracks, mainly albedo, to the data sample.

Track pointing to the collision vertex in the xy plane

The first indication for the discrepancy between data and simulation as far as the background level is concerned is related to the distribution of the minimum distance of tracks to the collision vertex in the xy plane. The figures 5 and 13 in Ref. [1] show these distributions for data and simulation, respectively. Apparently, the peak visible at small transverse distance in those figures corresponds to tracks of primary particles while the tail towards larger distances is due to contributions from non-primary particles, mainly albedo.

In order to compare those two distributions, we rebin them so that one bin corresponds to a distance of 5 cm and normalize them relative to each other at the first bin. The resulting spectra are shown in the upper panel of Fig. 1. The primary particle contribution to the distance distribution is contained almost completely in the first bin, while the remaining bins are dominated by background. The lower panel of Fig. 1 shows the ratio of the normalized transverse-distance distributions of data and simulation. By definition, the ratio in the lowest bin is equal to one.

It is obvious that the background level in the data is larger compared to the simulation by about a factor of two. Furthermore, the fact that the ratio does not show a significant dependence on the transverse distance proves that the shape of the simulated distance distribution is consistent with the measurement. To perform our final background subtraction we will make use of this observation as described in section 3 of the present analysis note.

Track pointing to the collision vertex in the Rz plane

The second indication for the underestimate of the background level in the simulation can be obtained from the small fraction of tracks measured in the drift chambers where tracking was not only performed in the xy plane but the track has been fully reconstructed in three dimensions using the stereo-wire nets of the drift chambers. Unfortunately, the stereo-wire coverage is rather marginal in this first run of the experiment and this is why the present analysis is restricted to track projections into the xy plane in first place.

In order to determine whether a track points back to the collision vertex in the plane radius versus z (Rz plane), we calculate for fully reconstructed tracks the z coordinate at the 3d space point where the track reaches the minimum distance to the collision vertex in the xy plane. From this value we subtract the z coordinate of the collision vertex as reconstructed with the beam-beam counter (BBC).

The resulting distance distributions are shown in Fig. 2 for various cuts on the DC tracks. The top (black) curve corresponds to tracks where 3d reconstruction was possible but no further cuts have been applied. The peak close to a distance of 0 cm corresponds to tracks pointing back to the collision vertex in the Rz plane. The small deviation of the peak from zero towards a negative distance reflects the status of the present quality of the detector alignment in the runs analyzed. The cutoff of the distance distribution at about ± 45 cm is due to a feature of the reconstruction

algorithm for drift-chamber tracks. If a track does not point back in the Rz plane to the collision vertex as measured with the BBC reasonably well its stereo-wire information is discarded and tracking is performed only in the xy plane. Consequently, the background level estimated from the distributions shown in Fig. 2 corresponds only to a lower limit of the true background level.

If we require more stringent selection cuts on the quality of the track reconstruction, the background contribution to the distance distribution decreases and, simultaneously, the ratio of the signal (Gaussian peak on top of flat background) to the total intensity (S/T) increases as shown in Fig. 2. For tracks which point back to the vertex in the xy plane the ratio S/T increase from 40% to 50%. If, in addition, we require cuts on a minimum number of 4 stereo (UV) wire hits associated to the track and that all 4 stereo-wire nets have contributed hits to the track, the S/T ratio increases further to 63% and 70%, respectively. Under these most stringent conditions, we expect that for almost all tracks the pointing in the Rz plane is accurate within a few cm. We therefore conclude that the background contribution to our track sample is larger than $(1 - 0.7) = 0.3$. This lower limit has to be compared with the value

0.209 which has been extracted from our Monte Carlo simulation as discussed in Ref. [1].

Transverse-momentum distributions

The third indication for an underestimate of the background level in our simulation comes from the measured transverse-momentum distributions as discussed in detail in Ref. [2]. In that analysis note it has been shown that reconstruction efficiency for the transverse momentum p_t of primary particles is independent on the reconstructed p_t in the p_t range from 0.6 GeV/c to 1.2 GeV/c (compare Figs. 16a and 16b in Ref. [2]). We therefore normalize the uncorrected measured p_t distributions of particles with negative and positive charge (taken from Fig. 10 in Ref. [2]), respectively, to the corresponding spectra reconstructed from simulated data in that p_t range and calculate the ratio of data and simulation. The result is shown in Fig. 3. An increase of the ratio data/MC by more than 50% in the p_t range between 1 and 3 GeV/c is visible. Above transverse momenta of 3 GeV/c statistics gets poor. As has been discussed in Ref. [2], the contribution of non-primary particles to the p_t spectra increases with increasing p_t (see Fig. 12a in Ref. [2]). Especially, above 2 GeV/c albedo starts to dominate the transverse-momentum distributions. Therefore, the apparent increase of the ratio of the p_t distributions obtained from data and simulation, respectively, can be interpreted as an indication for an underestimate of the background level in our simulation.

Final correction for the vertex-pointing cut

We have shown by three independent methods that compared to the data the background level is underestimated in the simulation by about a factor of 2. For the final background subtraction in our charged-particle multiplicity analysis we make use of the fact that the simulation describes the shape of the background contribution to the transverse-distance distribution very well. We therefore scale the contribution from non-primary particles to that distribution in the simulation relative to the contribution from primary particles. Doing that, we are able to reproduce the measured transverse-distance distribution as demonstrated in Fig. 4.

The contribution of non-primary particles to the sample of tracks accepted after the cut on the transverse distance to the collision vertex in the xy plane is 40.6%. This has to be compared to the value 20.9% which we had obtained before applying a proper scaling of the background in the simulation (see Sec. 5.3 in Ref. [1]).

In addition to the correction for the background contribution, we still have to correct for the fact that a small fraction of primary tracks is lost due to resolution if we cut on the vertex pointing in the xy plane. However, this correction is small compared to the background correction.

The systematic error of the vertex-pointing correction has two contributions:

1. Resolution
2. Background subtraction

As discussed already in Ref. [1] the systematic error due to resolution can be estimated by applying a cut of $4 \pm$

1 cm^1 on the transverse distance in the simulation, where the cut at 4 cm (instead of the 5 cm cut used for the data) takes into account the better resolution in the simulation compared to the data. The uncertainty in the cut of $\pm 1 \text{ cm}$ translates into a relative systematic uncertainty of 6.5%.

The relative systematic error due to the background-subtraction procedure has been estimated in the following way. The scaling factor for the background contribution in the simulation is fixed within a few percent as the ratio plot in the lower panel of Fig. 4 shows. The systematic error due to the absolute value of the scaling factor is therefore small. Nevertheless, some uncertainty is in the procedure since the non-primary particle background contains contributions from decays and from albedo which should not scale the same. In fact, in first order the background due to decays of

primary particles should be correctly described in the simulation and only the albedo contribution is to be scaled up relative to the primary-particle contribution. In the present PISA simulation framework the capabilities to distinguish decays from albedo are limited. Nevertheless, we could separate the background contributions from non-primary particles into two classes:

- non-primary particles where the parent is a primary (mainly decays)
- non-primary particles where the parent itself is a non-primary (mainly albedo)

These two classes of background have then been scaled independently to describe the measured transverse-distance distribution. The resulting variation of the relative contribution of background to the accepted track sample allowed us to estimate a relative systematic uncertainty of about 8% due to the background-subtraction procedure.

In summary, the proper subtraction of background requires the following correction factor to the multiplicity of tracks pointing back to the vertex in the xy plane:

$$\epsilon_{vertex} = 0.612 \quad (1)$$

This has to be compared to the incomplete correction factor of 0.828 used in Ref. [1].

We estimate the relative systematic uncertainty as $\sqrt{0.065^2 + 0.08^2} = 0.10$

Result

The final corrected multiplicity M_{corr} is calculated from M_{cut}^{west} and M_{cut}^{east} according to (for the abbreviation used see Ref. [1]):

$$M_{corr} = (M_{cut}^{west} / \epsilon_{DC}^{west} + M_{cut}^{east} / \epsilon_{DC}^{east}) * (\epsilon_{ghost} / \epsilon_{track}) * (\epsilon_{vertex} / \epsilon_{decay}) / (\epsilon_{\Delta\phi} * \epsilon_{\Delta\eta}) \quad (2)$$

The relative systematic errors summarized in the following have been described and estimated in Ref. [1] and above:

- $\epsilon_{\Delta\phi}$: 1.3%
- $\epsilon_{\Delta\eta}$: 2.5%
- $\epsilon_{DC}^{west} + \epsilon_{DC}^{east}$: 3.5%
- ϵ_{track} : 6.6%
- ϵ_{ghost} : 1%
- ϵ_{vertex} : 10%
- ϵ_{decay} : 4.7%

Summing these uncertainties quadratically yields a total systematic uncertainty of 14%.

The resulting distribution is shown in Fig. 5 together with the corresponding result from a cluster correlation analysis of the pad chambers PC1 and PC3 (see Ref. [3]). The shapes of both distributions are almost identical. Judged from the endpoints of the two distributions at large multiplicity it is obvious that the two measurements agree to 6%, well within our systematic errors.

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Figures

Figure 1: Transverse distance of tracks to the collision vertex from data and simulation. The upper panel shows the distributions on an absolute scale where data and simulation have been normalized to each other in the first bin. The lower panel shows the ratio of data and simulation.

Figure 2: Longitudinal distance of tracks to the collision vertex for various cuts on the reconstructed tracks (see text.)

Figure 3: Ratio of the transverse-momentum distributions obtained from data and simulation, respectively, shown separately for negative and positive particles. The original spectra were taken from Ref. [2].

Figure 4: Transverse distance of tracks to the collision vertex from data and simulation after scaling the relative contribution from non-primary particles in the simulation. The upper panel shows the distributions on an absolute scale where data and simulation have been normalized to each other in the first bin. The lower panel shows the ratio of data and corrected simulation.

Figure 5: Fully corrected pseudo-rapidity density distribution for charged particles at mid rapidity in min. bias Au + Au collisions at a cms energy of $\sqrt{s} = 130$ GeV in the nucleon-nucleon system. The result of the present analysis is compared to the result of an analysis based on the information from the Pad chambers PC1 and PC3 (taken from Ref. [3]).

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Minimum Bias Multiplicity Distribution at $\sqrt{s} = 130$ A GeV Using the PHENIX Pad Chambers

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Abstract

This is the final analysis note describing the procedure used and the results obtained in the determination of the charged particle pseudo-rapidity density $dN_{ch}/d\eta$ in Au-Au collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 130$ A GeV. The analysis is primarily based on the information from the Pad Chambers PC1 and PC3 of the PHENIX central east arm, but it also uses the ZDC and BBC counters both for the selection of minimum bias events and for the determination of the vertex position.

For the sake of completeness we include material that has already been presented in previous versions of this analysis [1, 2, 3].

1 Trigger, event selection and minimum bias sample size

The results presented here were derived from the measurements performed at $\sqrt{s} = 130$ A GeV with B=0 at the end of the year-1 run when the PHENIX central arms were located in their nominal position. More specifically, the runs we have analyzed are shown in Table 1.

In all these files, the trigger was defined by the ZDC (bit 0x2) and the BBCLL1 (bit 0x1000). All events with BBCLL1 trigger fired were written to tape and were flagged by the presence of bit 0x1000 in the trigger pattern. All events with BBCLL1 & ZDC in coincidence were also written to tape and had both bits on in the trigger pattern. Finally the events with ZDC trigger, scaled down by a factor of 1-60, were also written to tape and had the first bit on in the trigger pattern. This resulted in three types of events: BBCLL1 exclusive triggers (pattern 0x1000), BBCLL1&ZDC triggers (pattern 0x1002) and ZDC scaled down exclusive triggers (pattern 0x2).

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Table 1: Runs with Zero magnetic field.

Run series	Date	Run numbers	Events
8000	Aug,8,2000	8881, 8882, 8884,	14203
10000	Aug,18,2000	10507, 10510, 10515, 10523, 10525, 10527, 10545, 10603, 10629, 10643, 10645, 10647, 10651, 10679, 10706, 10708,	124879
11000	Aug,27,2000	11797, 11801, 11805, 11807, 11814	154298

Figure 1: Vertex position distributions for the three different triggers. The vertex position was derived from the ZDC for the BBCLL1&ZDC and ZDC-only triggers and from the BBC for the BBC-only triggers.

The vertex position distribution for the different triggers is shown in Figure. 1, covering a very broad range along the beam axis. The present analysis is restricted to collisions around the center of the interaction region. The off-line event selection required the vertex to be reconstructed by the ZDC within $|z| \leq 17.0$ cm. (This choice was dictated by the small trigger inefficiency seen in Figure 1 around $|z| \sim 20.0$ cm, which was caused by the on-line BBC vertex restriction applied in the last runs). The analysis included also all events where only the BBCLL1 trigger fired. For this class of events the vertex was taken from the BBC (of course requiring $|z| \leq 17.0$ cm).

We have also discarded a small number of events (a total of 1329 events) from BBCLL1 inclusive trigger which have a small or equal to zero average amplitude per photomultiplier as shown in Figure 2. The number of events satisfying these conditions is shown in Table 2 for the various triggers, resulting in a total sample size of 230544 minimum bias events³. This total number of events is taken to reflect the total minimum bias cross section (the sum of nuclear interaction part + the Coulomb double dissociation

³Since there has been a lot of discussion on the scale down of ZDC events we give in Appendix 1 a description and explanation of the procedure used to derive the total number of minimum bias events.

part) equal to 10.7 barns [4]. The paper is restricted to the analysis of the 137784 events with inclusive BBCLL1 trigger. This number is taken to reflect 92% of the total nuclear interaction cross section equal to 7.2 barns.

Table 2: Sample Size (ZDC vertex $|z| \leq 17.0$ cm)

Run series	8000	10000	11000	Rejected	Total
ZDC&BBCLL1	1778	27646	106239	880	134783
BBCLL1 only	59	1033	2358	449	3001
ZDC only	1110	3045	1223		92760
ZDC Scaling factor	1	6	60		
Total	2947	46949	181977		230544

Figure 3 shows the correlation between the analog response of the ZDC and the BBC for the three different triggers. The middle panel, for BBC exclusive triggers, shows a very small fraction of events, at the sub-percent level, with high BBC and low ZDC response which presumably represent the inefficiency of the ZDC trigger for central collisions. However, most events in the middle panel have a sizable ZDC response and yet the ZDC

Figure 2: The left figure shows the BBC amplitude. BBCLL1&ZDC trigger events with zero amplitude are discarded. The right picture shows the average amplitude per photo-tube. Events with low average amplitude are discarded.

trigger did not fire. It is not clear whether or not these events are valid. As mentioned above, all events with BBC-only trigger are included in the present analysis. However, Table 2 shows that they represent only 2.2 % of the total sample of BBC inclusive events.

Figure 3: Correlation of BBC and ZDC analog response for the various triggers

2 Vertex

As mentioned in the previous section, events were selected to have a vertex at $|z| \leq 17.0$ cm determined from the ZDC. However, for the track reconstruction, we used the best vertex position available using the following hierarchy: the first choice is always the vertex derived from PC1/3. As second choice we take the vertex reconstructed from BBC. This occurs for low-multiplicity events where the number of tracks is too small to allow a PC

vertex determination, (i.e. less than ~ 5 tracks in one arm). If both vertices are missing then the vertex position is taken from ZDC.

The vertex distributions from the different subsystems are shown in Figure 4. The vertical bars show the acceptance boundary of $|z| \leq 17.0$ cm. The differences between

Figure 4: Vertex distributions from the different subsystems. Acceptance window is shown with two vertical bars.

vertices reconstructed from PC-BBC, and PC-ZDC are shown in Figure 5 demonstrating

Figure 5: Comparison of the vertices reconstructed from PC, BBC and ZDC.

good agreement between all three subsystems. There is an offset of the order 0.5cm between the PC and BBC vertices. This causes no problems since the R cut value (see Section 3) is comparatively very large.

2.1 Vertex determination from PC1-PC3.

The straight line obtained by combining every hit in PC3 to every hit in PC1 defines a track if it intersects the plane $X=0$ within an appropriate rectangular window (± 90 cm in the Z direction i.e. much larger than the distance between the magnet poles and ± 8 cm in the Y direction). For each event we determine the distribution of the intersection points along the Z-coordinate (i.e. the beam direction). An attempt is made to fit it with a gaussian function plus a constant. If the fit is successful (i.e. more than 3 tracks under the peak above the background level and a width smaller than 5 cm), the mean of the gaussian function is accepted as the event vertex position. The geometry of PC1 and PC3 and the projection plane can be seen in Figure 6. Note that the projection plane is inclined

Figure 6: Geometry of the Pad chambers.

by 11.25° with respect to the real PHENIX $X=0$ plane due to the inclination of the East arm. Three examples of reconstructed vertices for events with different multiplicities are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Examples of vertices reconstructed with PC1 and PC3.

3 Track selection.

3.1 Algorithm.

Once the vertex is known, we combine again all hits in PC3 to all hits in PC1. The straight line going through each pair of hits defines a track if it intersects the plane $X=0$ within an appropriate circular window of radius R from the vertex position. The geometry is the same as shown in Figure 6. The resulting R distribution is shown in Figure 8. The

Figure 8: Tracks per event as a function of the distance to the event vertex.

vertical scale shows the absolute number of tracks per event and per cm for events in Table 2. The figure also shows the two components of tracks contributing to the total distribution:

- the combinatorial background contribution which is inherent to the algorithm used. It can be easily determined by using a mixed event technique. In this analysis, the background was determined by exchanging each sector in PC1 with its neighbor. The background yield increases quadratically with R (resulting in a linear dependence in the R distribution in Figure 8) ⁴.

- the real tracks contribution which is readily obtained by subtracting the background from the total ($N_{real} = N_{tot} - N_{bg}$). One observes a sharp peak at small R - these are primary tracks originating at the vertex - and a long tail due to decay products of a primary particle decaying in flight (see [8]) ⁵.

3.2 Background subtraction.

The combinatorial background can be determined and subtracted event-by-event. However, this would introduce an unnecessary broadening of the real multiplicity distribution. In order to avoid that, we perform an average background subtraction, exploiting the clear correlation which exists between N_{bg} and N_{tot} . Figure 9 shows a scatter plot of N_{bg} (cal-

Figure 9: Number of shuffled background tracks vs number of total. Bins of 1,2, or 3 are used to derive average value (shown by red circles) and error bars.

⁴We also tried different methods: we interchanged the four top PC1 with the four bottom PC1 chambers, and the full East arm of PC1 with the full PC1 West arm. All 3 methods give the same result. We have also checked with PISA, using HIJING Au-Au min bias events at $\sqrt{s} = 130\text{GeV}$, that the number of reshuffled tracks is on the average equal to the number of combinatorial background tracks within an accuracy better than 1%.

⁵Note that a primary charged particle or a primary neutral particle decaying in flight might contribute to this tail. This issue will be further discussed in more detail in Subsection 5.3.

culated event-by-event by the mixing procedure) vs. N_{tot} . The red points represent the average values of the background for a given number of total tracks. The average background is very well defined with very small error bars almost everywhere, except at very high multiplicities where we run out of statistics and where the average points can be approximated by a straight line. So in the present analysis, for each event with N_{tot} we subtract the corresponding average background given in Figure 9. With this approach we don't need to make any assumptions concerning relations between hits and tracks, as we did when we were limited by statistics [3].

We have studied the shape of the real track distribution in the 8 sectors of PC1. The results are shown in Figure 10. The two curves in each panel represent the north and

Figure 10: Tracks per event in different sectors of the Pad Chambers.

south distributions. As one can see the shape of the distribution is quite independent of

geometry or acceptance ⁶.

3.3 Fraction of accepted tracks.

The dashed' curve in Figure 8, obtained after subtraction of the background, shows the number of real tracks as a function of R. In practice, the track counting is performed up to a given R value. The fraction of counted real tracks as a function of R is given by the integral of the dashed curve (hatched area) normalized to the total integral up to $R = \infty$. (The tail due to decays at large R values is very well described by an exponential function as shown in Figure 8 and therefore the extrapolation of the green curve to $R = \infty$ is straightforward). The results are shown in Figure 11. The fraction of accepted tracks

Figure 11: Fraction of accepted tracks as a function of acceptance window.

for a large enough R-window (>20 cm) changes insignificantly when considering all PC1 sectors or if one restricts the analysis to the four central sectors. There is also practically no difference if one selects only events with high multiplicity.

In the present analysis the track counting was performed up to the value of $R = 25$ cm. This choice ensures that a very large fraction, 95.9%, of the real tracks is counted. At large R values the combinatorial background is larger than the signal as seen in Figure 8. However, this does not represent any problem since the background subtraction is a reliable operation (as discussed above).

⁶The pathology referred to as the misalignment problem observed in Sector 0 in earlier versions of this analysis disappeared after using the proper Pad Geometry file. The effect seen in sectors 4 and 5 is due to HV trip in PC3 in this area. As one can see it cancels out in this two sectors

3.4 Comparison to PISA simulations.

The whole procedure of combining hits of PC1 and PC3 to determine the collision vertex, define tracks, and subtract the background was first established using HIJING-generated events⁷ of Au-Au collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 130$ A GeV passed through PISA [1]. In this section we demonstrate the validity of the procedure and we show an absolute comparison of PISA results and data.

In Figure 12 the blue curve represents the raw multiplicity distribution given by PISA whereas the red curve is the distribution obtained by submitting the PISA output to the full analysis procedure (i.e. vertex reconstruction, track determination and background subtraction⁸). The comparison assumes a perfect double hit resolution and the good agreement between the two curves serves as justification of the analysis procedure.

Figure 12: Comparison of particle multiplicity distributions obtained from PISA. The blue curve shows the distribution making use of the GEANT information. The red curve is the result of the procedure using total number of tracks and background subtraction by shuffling PC1 sectors.

Figure 13 compares the R distribution of the data and PISA. The figure also shows the magnitude of the combinatorial background derived from the data and PISA. One sees that the background is not properly accounted for in the simulations. The data have approximately 85% more background tracks (not originating directly from the collision) or equivalently approximately 36% more hits than in the simulations. However, if one looks at the distribution of real tracks, after background subtraction, the agreement between data and simulation is good as demonstrated in Figure 14. The data have a lower peak and a wider distribution compared to PISA, possibly due to more multiple scattering,

⁷Event generator HIJING version 1.33

⁸In order to take into account the intrinsic position resolution of the chambers, the PISA hits were gaussian smeared in PC1 with a σ of 1.8 and 3.6mm in the Z and Y directions, respectively [6]. The corresponding numbers for PC3 were 2.5 and 5 mm.

Figure 13: Number of accepted tracks per event obtained from data and simulation.

geometry misalignments and detector resolution. The tail of the distribution reflecting the in-flight decay of particles is almost identical in both cases. The fraction of tracks accepted by the cut at $R=25\text{cm}$ is found to be in good agreement, 95.9% for the data and 96.9% for PISA.

Figure 14: Comparison of real tracks per event from data and simulation.

4 Raw distributions.

4.1 Distributions of hits and tracks.

Figure 15 shows the hit distribution in the various pad chambers. The PC1 distributions in the West and East arms are in excellent agreement. PC3 shows slightly less hits due to

Figure 15: Hit distribution in the Pad Chambers.

larger inactive gaps in the chambers, more ROC's that were either hot or inactive and a temporarily disabled HV sector. Figure 15 also shows the PC1 hit distribution obtained from PISA, directly demonstrating that the data has $\sim 36\%$ more hits than PISA predicts, as already mentioned. Figure 16 shows the hit distribution in PC1-East, the total track distribution and the associated combinatorial background in the East arm.

Figure 16: Hits, combinatorial background and tracks in the Pad Chambers.

4.2 Raw multiplicity distribution.

The raw multiplicity distribution of real tracks (after subtracting the combinatorial background) in the East arm and taking into account the scale-down factor of the ZDC exclusive triggers is shown in Figure 17. The contributions from the different triggers are also shown. The intermittent HV sector in PC3 is also taken into account. The shape of the distribution at high multiplicities is binomially broadened by the limited acceptance of one single arm. For the multiplicity distribution in one unit of rapidity and 2π azimuthal coverage, the broadening is estimated to have a width of ~ 8 tracks at the highest multiplicities.

Figure 17: Raw multiplicity distribution of “real” tracks in one single arm. without corrections. The distributions are plotted for all events and for each of the three triggers.

A relevant check is the comparison of the raw multiplicity distribution obtained from the three sets of runs listed in Tables 1 and 2, which have different scale-down factors. The three distributions are overlaid in Figure 18 after normalizing them to the “11000” data set (see Tables 1 and 2).

5 Corrections.

5.1 Scaling correction factors.

There are several correction factors which we have to apply in order to get the correct number of tracks in one PHENIX arm. Most of them are scaling factors of trivial origin and they are listed in Table 3 together with the uncertainties in their determination. Some additional comments are given below.

The uncertainty in the number of tracks outside the R acceptance cut derives from a comparison of this correction factor obtained under different conditions (multiplicity,

Figure 18: Raw multiplicity distribution of “real” tracks in one single arm without corrections for three different sets of files, normalized to the integral of set “11000”.

Table 3: Scaling correction factors

Origin	Total	%	Accuracy
Tracks outside R acceptance of 25cm		4.1%	$\pm 1.5\%$
PC1- ϕ dead area (construction)	21mrad	1.3%	last digit
PC1- θ dead area (construction)	2.3mrad	0.2%	last digit
PC3- ϕ dead area (construction)	63mrad	4.0%	last digit
PC3- θ dead area (construction)	26mrad	3.6%	last digit
PC1 inactive ROCs	10	1.4%	$\pm 0.4\%$
PC3 inactive ROCs	27	3.8%	$\pm 1.0\%$
PC1 dead pads	20	0.2%	last digit
PC3 dead pads	220	1.9%	$\pm 0.5\%$
PC1 intrinsic inefficiency		0.6%	+0.5%
PC3 intrinsic inefficiency		0.6%	+0.5%
In-flight particle decays		2.8%	$\pm 4\%$
Total losses		22.1%	

sectors, cut value) and comparisons to PISA. The quality of the exponential fit shown in Figure 8 is also taken into account.

The uncertainty assigned to inactive ROCs and dead pads are estimates.

The PC1 and PC3 intrinsic efficiency was measured using cosmic rays and found to be better than 99% [5] in agreement with an analytical study of the pad chamber performance [6]. Another measurement of the PC1 intrinsic efficiency using the real data was done using DC tracks projections into PC1 and found to be 98% but this number includes also the PC1 dead areas [7].

The correction due to particle decay in-flight and its associated error are discussed

in Section 5.3.

5.2 Double hit resolution correction

In order to avoid the generation of ghost hits[12, 13] in PC1/3 when two hits come close to each other, we forced the merging of hits closer than 4 cm in PC1 and 8 cm in PC3, in other words we have imposed an off-line double hit resolution (dhr) of 4 and 8 cm in PC1 and PC3 respectively. These numbers were chosen such that they practically eliminate the ghost problem and are not much larger than the intrinsic PC dhr which is ~ 3.5 cm in PC1 and twice that in PC3⁹.

One may argue that the chosen values of 4/8cm are too large compared to the single hit resolution (shr) of the chambers. In the PC structure with 9 pixels = 1 pad, what matters for the dhr is the length of the pad (not the length of the pixel) which is $\sim 3 \times 8.4$ mm. Hits closer than 3 pixels can practically never be resolved, the minimum distance to resolve two hits is 4 pixels e.i. approximately 34mm in PC1. This is a pure design feature. So the value of 4cm chosen to eliminate the ghost problem is reasonable. In other words, the PC structure of 9pixels/pad preserves a very good shr, allows to save an order of magnitude in the number of electronic channels but with the price of sacrificing on the dhr.

The intrinsic dhr could be improved with a cluster splitting algorithm, however the procedure of cluster splitting itself needs careful study before it can be used since it could also be another potential source of ghost hits.

The dhr has several impacts on the analysis procedure. Below, we discuss them in detail.

5.2.1 DHR effect on hit and track losses.

The hit loss depends quadratically on the number of hits. The fraction of hits lost by the dhr is:

$$f = \frac{(N - 1)}{2} \times \frac{\pi r^2}{S} \quad (1)$$

and the remaining number of hits in the chamber is then:

$$N' = N - \frac{N(N - 1)}{2} \times \frac{\pi r^2}{S} \quad (2)$$

where N is the real number of hits in the pad chamber, r is the double hit resolution (4 cm and 8 cm), and S is the total area of the chamber. This formula is accurate (provided $\pi r^2/S \ll 1$) for randomly distributed hits over a given area and it can easily be derived. It was checked using a simple simulation, and also on PISA results (but after removing correlations between hits, i.e. after removing hits originating from π^0 Dalitz decays and from γ conversions).

The loss of hits induces a loss of tracks. We have debated at length what is that matters for the dhr correction on the track counting, the total number of hits or the total

⁹The forced merging of hits is done in the following way: after the hit reconstruction, all hits are scanned and whenever two hits are closer than 4cm in PC1, one of them chosen randomly is removed, and similarly for PC3.

number of real tracks? We performed Monte Carlo studies which convinced us that it is the number of hits which matters and allowed us to develop the following procedure to correct for the effect of dhr on the track counting: for each event we know the measured number of tracks, the number $N1'$ of hits in PC1 and the number $N3'$ of hits in PC3. From the equation above we calculate the real number of hits $N1$ and $N3$ and the ratios $R1 = N1'/N1$ and $R3 = N3'/N3$ for PC1 and in PC3, respectively. The measured number of tracks was then divided by the product of these two ratios. In other words the fraction of lost tracks is equal to the product of the fractions of lost hits in PC1 and PC3. This procedure was developed and checked using PISA.

5.2.2 DHR effect on the background subtraction.

The dhr also affects the background subtraction in the sense that the event combinatorial background is overestimated by the background determined by a mixing event technique.

Let **Total** be the total number of hits in the PC. It consists of two components: **Real** hits which have a correlated hit in the other PC produced by the same particle or its ancestor, such that the associated track falls within the acceptance window and **Background** hits e.i. are all other hits which do not have a partner hit in the other PC and are produced by particles coming from walls, large opening angle decays, or particles missing one of the PCs.

The total number of reconstructed tracks in the event consists of a **Real** component (the number of real tracks is the same as the number of real hits by definition) and a component which is an **Accidental** background. This background consists itself of three parts which to first order are proportional to the products of number of hits: **Background** \times **Background**, **Background** \times **Real**, and **Real** \times **Real**. Both the **Real** and the **B** \times **B** components are reduced by dhr as discussed in the previous sub-section. However, the number of **B** \times **R** and **R** \times **R** accidental tracks is reduced even faster. This is explained below with the help of Figure 19¹⁰.

Let's consider an accidental track built by **B** \times **B** (blue circles) hits, case A1. This track can merge with another track if there is a hit of any origin (open circle) close to one of these hits, e.g. in PC3 as pictured in case A2. The probability that such a hit will be found is given by the formula discussed above.

Let's now consider an accidental track of type **B** \times **R** (blue and red circles) pictured in case B1. As before, there must be another hit for a track to disappear. Besides any random hit which can be found close by as in the **B** \times **B** track case, there is a big probability to find another hit in PC3 within the acceptance R window, namely the partner hit of the **Real** (red circle) hit in PC1 (case B2) thus leading to a track loss. This probability does not depend on the PC occupancy and the additional track loss is proportional to the dhr-to-acceptance window ratio. One should note that for an accidental track of the type **R** \times **R** the additional track loss is doubled because each hit has a close partner in the same PC.

This effect disappears in the mixed event. Once we interchange the PC1 sectors (or any other event mixing technique) all **Real** hits in the PCs are converted into **Background** hits by breaking all correlations between them. Therefore, in the direct event the

¹⁰This effect was found and studied independently by WIS group and Lund University group. The results are in good agreement.

Figure 19: Different types of accidental background affected by hit merging due to finite dhr.

number of **Accidental** tracks is smaller than the number of tracks in the mixed event. The two are related by:

$$Accidental = Mixed \left(1 - 4 \frac{Real}{Total} \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^2 \right) \quad (3)$$

where $r = 4$ cm is the dhr value, $R = 25$ cm is the acceptance window. In the analysis we used $R = 26.5$ cm, optimized from simulation and reflecting the fact that in cases such as those depicted in Figure 19 case B2, two correlated hits can have a distance somewhat larger than the acceptance window R .

5.2.3 DHR impact on γ -conversions and π^0 Dalitz decays.

Tracks closely correlated in space have obviously a large probability to be lost by the dhr. The γ -conversions and π^0 Dalitz decays are the two major processes here. The original number of tracks from those two sources can not be recovered by the dhr correction described above. This issue was extensively discussed by Maguire [9].

From simulations we know that if a conversion occurs before PC1 both legs merge in PC1 and PC3 in almost all cases. Therefore, if in PISA we count one track for one conversion then the above correction restores the initial number of PISA tracks with an uncertainty below the percent level. This small correction is now linear with the number of tracks and is taken into account with other corrections due to in-flight particle decays (see below).

5.2.4 Simultaneous merging of hits in PC1 and PC3.

There is another effect similar to one discussed in the previous subsection which also occurs. When two hits of two close real tracks (not from γ -conversions and π^0 Dalitz decays) merge in one PC they can merge in the other with a high probability. We have simulated this process and found out that the highest number of track pairs merging in two PC simultaneously never exceeds 3% of the total number of tracks, which means that the maximum loss is 1.5% of the total number of tracks. We have absorbed this effect into our systematic errors.

5.2.5 DHR correction results comparison.

Several checks were made to make sure that the dhr correction works properly. WIS and Lund University used two different toy-models to simulate the problem and the results were in good agreement.

A straightforward comparison between input and reconstructed tracks using PISA turned out to be not meaningful because the total number of hits in the Pad Chambers in PISA is significantly smaller than in the data (see Figure 15), and consequently the background correction discussed above is not large enough. We therefore added 50% more hits to each PC in our simulations thereby increasing the dhr losses and could demonstrate good agreement between the input and reconstructed multiplicity distributions once the number of real tracks and the background are corrected as described above (Figure 20). A deviation at high multiplicities is expected because the smaller number of initial hits increases the fluctuations.

The most meaningful test is a comparison of the multiplicity distribution obtained with dhr of 4 and 8 cm in PC1 and PC3 respectively with the distribution obtained while imposing a 50% larger dhr in both PC1 and PC3. The “dead area” around each hit thus increases by a factor of 2.25 and also the fraction of lost hits increases by the same amount. For example, assuming that the total number of hits in PC1 is 300, the number of lost hits due to dhr would increase from 32 to 72. This is a dramatic change and the consistency between the two distributions provides a very powerful test of the whole analysis procedure and in particular of the corrections associated to hit merging and background subtraction. It also provides a good measure of the systematic errors inherent to the analysis procedure. The two distributions are shown in Figure 21. They coincide very well, the tail is broader for 6 cm dhr value as expected due to larger fluctuations.

Figure 20: Comparison of the multiplicity distributions obtained from PISA with 50% additional hits in each PC. The blue curve shows the reconstructed distribution in the ideal case ($dhr=0$). The red curve is the result of the whole analysis chain (forced hit merging, vertex and track reconstruction, background subtraction and dhr correction). The small correction for γ conversions is not applied.

Figure 21: Comparison of the corrected multiplicity distributions with dhr values of 4 cm (8cm) and 6 cm (12cm) in PC1 and PC3 respectively..

5.3 Correction due to in-flight particle decays

A large fraction of the in-flight decay of charged particles is detected and counted in our procedure as illustrated in Figure 8. However, a small fraction of those still remains

unaccounted for. On the other hand, there are decays of neutral particles leading to charged tracks. Those two effects have to be taken into account. Clearly the quantitative evaluation depends on the particle composition and on their momentum distribution. Lacking precise information about them, we made detailed studies using Monte Carlo simulations, by comparing the HIJING charged particle multiplicity in the East arm acceptance to the PISA results processed in exactly the same way as the real data. We have performed several comparisons of this type and always found that the missed tracks due to charged particle decays in flight are to a large extent compensated by the decay of neutral particles (mainly π^0 and K_S^0). For the present case, we found a net loss of 2.8% of the real tracks. The comparison is shown in Table 4. The total number of charged

Table 4: Particle composition per minimum bias event

Origin	Primary	Decay	Total	HIJING
$\pi^+\pi^-$	12.66	3.56	16.22	20.33
p^+p^-	0.69	0.12	0.80	0.92
K^+K^-	0.49	0.39	0.89	1.84
e^+e^-	0.02		0.02	0.02
Others ($\Sigma^\pm, \bar{\Sigma}^\pm, \Xi^\pm \dots$)		0.21	0.21	0.17
Charged	13.86	4.28	18.14	23.28
π^0		0.69	0.69	11.37
γ		0.06	0.06	2.26
n, \bar{n}		0.06	0.06	0.92
K_L^0		0.07	0.07	0.90
K_S^0		1.23	1.23	0.90
Others ($\Lambda, \Xi^0, \Sigma^0 \dots$)		0.33	0.33	0.33
Neutral		2.44	2.44	16.67
Total	13.86	6.71	20.57	39.95
Total corrected			22.63	

particles given by HIJING in one arm acceptance is 23.28 per minimum bias collision. The total number of detected tracks according to PISA is 20.57. The latter becomes 22.63 after correcting for the tracks outside the $R=25\text{cm}$ cut and for the construction dead area as included in the PISA file, thereby resulting in a net loss of 2.8% in the PISA result wrt to the HIJING input.

In order to estimate the uncertainty associated with the correction, we performed simulation varying the momentum distribution and the particle composition within $\pm 20\%$ of the HIJING values. From the induced changes we assign a systematic error of less than 4% to the in-flight decay correction (as listed in Table 3, see also comparison with retracted geometry in section 6.4).

5.4 Correction for uncorrelated events

There is a small number of events recorded by the PHENIX DAQ system while a ‘‘Reset’’ signal was sent to the PCs. In such events the information about the event number is wrong and the number of such events was estimated to be $\approx 2.3\%$ of the total [10].

We have an independent confirmation to that in our data by looking at the events

with different amplitude response in the BBC. For several high amplitude values there are always events which contribute to the zero bin. The fraction of the events is independent of the BBC amplitude as seen in Figure 22. We have found that the total number of

Figure 22: Track multiplicity distribution for different values of the BBC analog response. Focus on the zero bin

events in the zero bin which has to be subtracted is ≈ 4000 , or 2.8% of the total number of events.

6 Results

6.1 Corrected minimum bias multiplicity distribution in the East arm

Using the events of BBC inclusive trigger, dhr correction + in-flight particle decay correction) we obtain the minimum bias multiplicity distribution in one PHENIX central arm shown in Figure 23.

The figure shows also the distribution calculated with HIJING version 1.35. The calculation was done for the η acceptance of PHENIX but with a reduced acceptance in ϕ of 65° in order to properly incorporate the binomial broadening resulting from the limited east arm acceptance (solid angle + losses listed in Table 3 + dhr losses at high multiplicities). This is an absolute comparison, in the sense that the data and HIJING integrated yields are taken to represent 92% and 100% of the 7.2 b cross section, respectively. One can see that the data shows higher multiplicity than HIJING (will be quantified below).

Figure 23: Multiplicity distribution of charged particles in one central PHENIX arm compared to 120,000 HIJING 1.35 events passed through the PHENIX acceptance.

6.2 Scaling to one unit of rapidity

The track acceptance of PC1/3 is not exactly the same as the solid angle coverage of the PC1 or PC3 chambers because some tracks entering or leaving PC1 or PC3 at the edges of the acceptance can miss the other PC due to multiple scattering or particle decay in flight. We have determined the track acceptance from the data by looking at the edges of the track distribution in θ and ϕ . We found an acceptance of $\eta = \pm 0.35$ and $\phi = 88.4^\circ$. So the scaling factor for one unit of rapidity with 2π azimuthal coverage is 5.82.

6.3 $dN_{ch}/d\eta$ at mid-rapidity as function of centrality

In order to study the particle density as function of centrality, we use the ZDC vs BBC analog response to define various centrality bins. The ZDC vs. BBC plot was shown previously for the different triggers (see Figure 3) and it is repeated here for all triggers together. In this two-dimensional plot one can set centrality bins only up to the turnover region where there are ambiguities i.e only for the 20% most central collisions. In order to delineate the centrality contour in the turn-over region and to further extend the range of centrality cuts, we use the hits in PC1-West: for a given range of hits in PC1-West we determine the centroid of the corresponding events in the BBC - ZDC correlation plot. The black points in Figure 24 show the positions of these centroids. They can be fitted by a polynomial curve as shown by the solid line in Figure 25. Following the fitted line one can integrate events along the curve (each integration step is a slice between two lines perpendicular to the curve) and map the centrality contour down peripheral collisions. Following this procedure we define 10 centrality bins¹¹, from 0-5%, 5-10%,45-50% of the total cross section.

¹¹Further binning requires more precise study of the distribution around zero

Figure 24: ZDC vs BBC analog response for all events (red) and for events selected by a range of hits in PC1-West (blue). For each number of hits in PC1-West the mean of the distribution is indicated by the black points.

Figure 25: The percentile cuts in the ZDC vs BBC analog response.

The corresponding multiplicity distributions in PC1/3 are shown in Figure 26. From the average of the various bell curves we can therefore determine (after multiplying by the solid angle scaling factor) the pseudo-rapidity charged particle density $dN_{ch}/d\eta$ at mid-rapidity as function of centrality. The results are shown in Table 5.

Figure 26: Multiplicity distribution of charged particles in one central PHENIX arm for various centrality bins.

6.4 Systematic Errors

We discuss here the systematic errors in our results. We are not quoting statistical errors since they are below percent level.

Trigger efficiency.

After a long discussion it was decided that the BBC inclusive trigger represents $92\% \pm 3\%$ of the total geometrical cross section of 7.2 barns . This was derived from simulations using different models [11]. The uncertainty in the trigger efficiency induces an uncertainty in the average particle density as a function of centrality. These errors are quoted in the third column of Table 5.

Acceptance error. The acceptance error in the fourth column of Table 5 represents all errors which are multiplicity independent. Most of them were previously listed in

Table 5: Average multiplicity for the top 50% of the cross-section and errors.

Percentile of $\sigma_{geo}=(7.2 \text{ barns})$	$\langle dN_{ch}/d\eta \rangle$ $ \eta < 0.5$	BBC eff. $\pm 3\% \text{ error}$	Acceptance error	DHR induced error
0 - 5	622	± 3	± 29	± 23
5 - 10	498	± 5	± 23	± 15
10 - 15	413	± 6	± 19	± 10
15 - 20	344	± 7	± 16	± 7
20 - 25	287	± 8	± 13	± 5
25 - 30	235	± 9	± 11	± 3
30 - 35	188	± 9	± 9	± 2
35 - 40	147	± 9	± 7	± 1
40 - 45	115	± 8	± 5	± 1
45 - 50	89	± 7	± 4	± 1

Table 3 (the uncertainties in the number of tracks outside the R acceptance, active areas, detector intrinsic efficiencies and undetected decays). To these we have added two small errors, a 0.5% error induced by the vertex restriction and a 1% in the background subtraction derived from different methods of event mixing. All these errors were added in quadrature and resulted in a total uncertainty of 4.6%. The dominant factor comes from the undetected particles due to in-flight decays. This uncertainty was previously discussed. An independent experimental quantitative support to this estimate comes from the comparison with the results obtained with another data set while the east arm was in the so-called retracted position, which is ~ 45 cm from its nominal position. This comparison is discussed below.

Errors induced by the double hit resolution. The systematic errors of the analysis procedure are dominated by the uncertainties in the dhr corrections (which as discussed previously affects the track counting and also the background subtraction). The best indication about these uncertainties comes from the comparison to the results obtained by imposing a 50% larger dhr as shown in Figure 21. From this comparison one can set an upper limit to these errors.

In addition to that, we have attempted a quantitative estimate of this uncertainty. Using equations 2 and 3 one can write assuming that the number of hits is equal in PC1 and PC3 and keeping the first order correction only:

$$Real = \left[Total - Mixed \left(1 - 4 \frac{Real}{Total} \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^2 \right) \right] \times \left(1 + N \frac{\pi r^2}{S} \right) \quad (4)$$

where all notations are taken from 2 and 3. The number of *Mixed* tracks is proportional to number of N_{hits}^2 to a very high accuracy and the proportionality constant is $A = 0.0061$. It was checked that it does not depend on multiplicity and dhr. The $\frac{Real}{Total}$ is the parameter we have to “guess” from the beginning in order to get the correct result. The measured ratio is shown in Figure 27 and it has an average value $B = 0.33 \pm 0.02$. One can take the derivative of expression 4 keeping the significant terms only:

$$dReal = \left[4 \frac{A}{B} \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\delta B}{B} + 2 \frac{\delta r}{r} - 2 \frac{\delta R}{R} \right) + \frac{\pi r^2}{BS} \left(2 \frac{\delta r}{r} - \frac{\delta S}{S} \right) \right] Real^2 \quad (5)$$

As expected the accuracy is proportional to the multiplicity squared. One can calculate it for the highest multiplicity bin and scale it down for other bins. The sum of all terms is taken in quadrature. The following uncertainties are taken into account:

$\frac{\delta B}{B}$ from Figure 27 equal to 6%.

$\frac{\delta r}{r}$ from the fact that for very big hits one can have clusters merging at distances even larger than 4cm. We can estimate the uncertainty to be about the ratio of single hit to double hit resolution ratio, which is about 4%.

$\frac{\delta R}{R}$: the uncertainty comes from the fact that R here is somewhat larger than the 25cm acceptance and was found to be 26.5cm by optimization with an accuracy of the order of 0.5 cm i.e. a 2% uncertainty.

$\frac{\delta S}{S}$ is known to the same accuracy as the acceptance and we keep 1% uncertainty on this number.

Figure 27: Ratio of total number of Tracks vs Total number of Hits in PCs.

We assign an uncertainty of about 1% for the higher order corrections.

The simultaneous hit merging discussed above results in an uncertainty of the order of 1.5% at high multiplicities.

Plugging all those numbers in the formula above allows to derive the systematic uncertainties in the particle density as function of centrality. The numbers are quoted in the last column of Table 5. For example, for a total number of Real tracks in the East arm equal to 90 (this is the situation for the highest centrality bin) results in an error of 3.6%.

Comparison to retracted data We compare here the multiplicity distribution shown in Figure 26 to the distribution obtained with the East arm in the retracted position. This comparison suffers from a number of problems. First, the ZDC and BBC settings were changed several times during the early runs, and most of them were below the nominal values of the runs used in the main analysis. We are convinced, by looking at the hit distribution in the PC (Figure 28) that there was a trigger inefficiency in the low multiplicity events which cannot be corrected for. Secondly there was additional material in the acceptance (scintillators and protection rubber around the beryllium beam pipe) which produces a few more hits in the retracted position. Assuming that the inefficiency is negligible for high multiplicity events, one can still compare the two multiplicity distributions in the high-multiplicity region which is the most sensitive to the dhr and in-flight decay corrections. The comparison is shown in Figure 29.

Appendix 1: Scale-down factor for pedestrians

To the best of our knowledge, the trigger logic as described in Section 1 is as follows:

- All events with BBCLL1 trigger fired were written to tape and were flagged by the presence of bit 0x1000 in the trigger pattern.

Figure 28: Hit distribution in PC1 for the retracted and nominal PHENIX central arm position. The distributions are corrected for the dhr losses and the difference in geometrical acceptance and are normalized to match at the upper bins.

Figure 29: Multiplicity distribution in PHENIX central arm measured with retracted and nominal arm position. The two distributions are normalized in the region $N=50-100$. The statistical error bars in the retracted position are not negligible. For example for $N=100$ the yield is 130.

- All events were BBCLL1&ZDC fired in coincidence were also written to tape. Those events had the ZDC bit 0x2 and the BBCLL1 bit 0x1000 in the trigger pattern.

- ZDC-only triggers were also written to tape after scale down by a factor from 1-60 and had the bit 0x2 in the trigger pattern.

This logic can be schematically represented by the diagram in Figure 30 and results in three types of events:

- type 1: BBCLL1 exclusive triggers (pattern 0x1000)
- type 2: BBCLL1 & ZDC triggers (pattern 0x1002),
- type 3: ZDC scaled down exclusive triggers (pattern 0x2).

Figure 30: Trigger scheme.

The total number of minimum bias events is then equal to (events of type 1) + (events of type 2) + (events of type 3) * (scale-down factor)

You can convince yourself that this is correct in a number of ways. Here is one of them. In the absence of any BBCLL1 & ZDC coincidence it is clear that the total number of ZDC events is given by (events of type 3) * (scale-down factor). However, if there are coincidences, it may happen that the scale down unit fires TOGETHER with a coincidence BBCLL1 & ZDC. In such a case we will not get a type 3 event but a type 2 event. This will happen for a fraction of all the BBCLL1 & ZDC coincidences and this fraction is exactly 1/(scale-down factor). So the total number of type 3 events "lost" by that is: (events of type 2) / (scale-down factor). We must add them to the measured number of type 3 events in order to obtain the total number of ZDC events and that leads to the expression above.

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